

Harnessing AI and Data-Intensive Technologies

Deliverable 3.1: Anticipatory Ethics of Self-Sovereign Identity-version 1

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Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
AGI	Artificial General Intelligence
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CLTC	Centre for Long-Term Cybersecurity
CNA	Centre for Naval Analyses
CORDIS	Community Research and Development Information Service
DC	Doctoral Candidate
DCU	Dublin City University
EMM	Enterprise Mobility Management
EU	European Union
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IoT	Internet of Things
IT	Information Technology
KETs	Key Enabling Technologies
LEAs	Law Enforcement Agencies
MDM	Mis-, Dis-, Mal-information
NATO	North Atlantic Treaty Organisation
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PATSTAT	Worldwide Patent Statistical Database
PDF	Portable Document Format
PESTLE	Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal, and Environmental
R&D	Research and Development
RAND	Research and Development
RI/R&I	Research and Innovation
STEEPL-I	Social, Technological, Economic, Environmental, Political, Legal, Innovation
TUNA	Turbulence, Uncertainty, Novelty, Ambiguity
UAE	Unites Arab Emirates

UK	United Kingdom
USA/US	Unites States of America
UT	University of Twente

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The report constitutes Deliverable 3.1 of Work Package 3 of the MSCA HARNESS project, which aims to anticipate the joint ethical, social, and economic implications of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and data flows, with attention to the evolving regulatory frameworks and compliance mechanisms shaping these technologies in the European Union (EU). The deliverable is under Task 3.1, which aims at investigating the most appropriate anticipatory methods for exploring the future evolution of AI and data flows, and with reflecting on the benefits and limitations of such methods for this domain. The report sets out the rationale for adopting scenario building, which will be operationalised through a series of scenario building workshops planned for Autumn 2026, as the primary anticipatory method for the HARNESS project. The choice is motivated by the deep uncertainty and complexity characterising both the AI technologies under analysis, but also the regulatory landscape governing them, which together demand the exploration of a plurality of plausible futures. Scenario building is particularly well-suited to this purpose, enabling systematic reflection on the ethical, social, and economic plausible futures of AI and data flows in the EU. The report is structured in three parts. **Section 1** provides a descriptive account of scenario building, covering relevant basic terminology, its history, and key strengths and limitations. **Section 2** presents findings from a rapid literature review of relevant scenario studies, conducted to inform the design of the HARNESS workshops. **Section 3** outlines the workshop design for Autumn 2026, specifying the parameters chosen and the reasoning behind them. The scope of this report is therefore wider than the *Anticipatory Ethics of Self-Sovereign Identity*, and a more precise title would have been *Anticipatory Methods for Exploring the Impacts of AI and Data Flows*.

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INTRODUCTION

This report constitutes D3.1 of T3.1 within WP3 of the HARNESS project, the overarching objective of which is to anticipate the joint ethical, social, and economic impact of AI and data flows while considering the potential evolution of regulatory frameworks and compliance mechanisms in the EU. The scope is wider than the Anticipatory Ethics of Self-Sovereign Identity, and a more precise title would have been *Anticipatory Methods for Exploring the Impacts of AI and Data Flows*. Tasked with investigating the most appropriate anticipatory methods for this purpose, T3.1 can be used throughout WP3 if needed in the other tasks. For example, the methods developed and justified here could be applied in T3.3, where DCs can use them to explore more specific domains of their own research foci. This report sets out the reasoning behind the choice of adopting scenario building, delivered through three upcoming futures workshops in Fall 2026, as the primary anticipatory ethical method for exploring plausible futures of AI, data flows, and their governance in the European Union (EU).

Scenario building is a widely used method for generating and communicating views on how a subject of analysis, such as a specific technology, may evolve and what future impacts it may have (Armanto, 2024). In our case, the preliminary description of our object of analysis is *the joint ethical, social, and economic implications of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and data flows, as well as the potential evolution of regulatory frameworks and compliance mechanisms in the EU* (provided in HARNESS proposal). This requires anticipatory ethical analysis because both the AI technologies and the regulatory frameworks shaping them are still emerging, whereas the full spectrum of their intended and unintended outcomes on fundamental rights, the economy, and social welfare remain uncertain. In fact, *uncertainty* is the central epistemological problem motivating the field of anticipatory ethics of technology: it calls for systematic reflection on the emerging questions posed by technological developments whose ethical, social, and economic stakes cannot yet be fully known (Brey, 2012).

Among the methods available for anticipatory inquiry, this report reviews scenario building, “a tool that can be used to ask such questions and to deal with uncertainty in our operating environments” (Sabol & Delina, 2004). According to Sabol and Delina (2004), “scenario [building] is a globally recognised tool used by organisations and institutions as part of their strategic planning processes. It aims to facilitate creative thinking and generate new ideas, legitimise uncertainties, and provide opportunities for organisational learning. It also helps organisations anticipate change, improve reaction time, and clarify as well as manage risk” (p. 956). There are multiple approaches to scenario building and implementation modalities (from expert-led formats to participatory and collaborative ones that may also involve citizens) (Armanto, 2024). The appropriate design for workshops fostering scenario building depends on the research purpose, the geographical and temporal scope of the study, the maturity of the technology under analysis, and the resources available to the researchers, for instance. Another important factor that is considered is findings from relevant literature, broadly construed. In light of these considerations, our planned workshops in Fall 2026

adopt an expert-based approach to exploratory scenario building to address the research challenges and research objectives of WP3, namely anticipating the ethical, social, and economic impact of AI and data flows and appraising the legal instruments, technological devices, and social institutions implicated in their governance, and this report aims at setting out the rationale behind that approach.

- **Section 1** offers a descriptive account of: (a) the emergence of scenario building as a foresight method, (b) the process by which scenarios are constructed in futures workshop settings, and (c) the approach's strengths and limitations as identified in the academic literature.
- **Section 2** presents findings from a rapid literature review conducted at this stage, aimed at informing the design of the upcoming HARNESS scenario-building study. The sources were selected for their thematic proximity to our topic and to the consortium's broader research scope, namely EU digital governance, AI, and data flows.
- **Section 3** explains the rationale for our methodological choices of our Autumn 2026 futures workshops, informed both by the preceding research and by the material and time resources available to us.

1. THE SCENARIO BUILDING APPROACH

1.1 History and Rationale for the Approach

Prior to tracing the history and applications of the scenario building method, it is necessary to clarify what a “scenario” actually is in futures studies, considering Glenn's (2009) observation that “scenario is probably the most abused term in futures research”; a scenario is “a story with plausible cause and effect links that connects a future condition with the present, while illustrating key decisions, events, and consequences throughout the narrative” (p. 2). Equally, “scenario planning” and “scenario building” (or “scenario analysis”) are two terms that necessitate clarification: “scenario planning” implies that scenarios are necessarily tied to decision-making and planning capacities. “Scenario building” (or “scenario analysis”) by contrast, is a broader term that accommodates a wider range of uses of scenarios without necessarily presupposing that the exercise culminates in any strategic decision or organisational plan. This flexibility makes it the more appropriate term for the present study, which seeks to explore plausible futures of AI, data flows, and their governance in the EU as an anticipatory ethical exercise, rather than to produce a roadmap for a specific institution's strategic choices. “Scenario building” is therefore the preferred term adopted throughout this report.

As Varum and Melo (2010) document, scenario building has its roots in post-war military strategy, where it was first developed as a method for defence planning, before being extended to social forecasting and public policy, most notably through the work of Herman Kahn, who is widely regarded as the founder of scenario building (Bradfield et al., 2006, cited in Varum and Melo, 2010). The method subsequently developed along two geographical areas: (a) in the United States, Kahn promoted scenario-building at RAND and French futurist Pierre Wack introduced the scenario approach as a strategic planning tool at the Royal Dutch/Shell Group in the early 1970s, with the technique later popularised by Schwartz and Van der Heijden, and (b) in Europe, whereby French philosopher and futurist Gaston Berger created normative scenarios and French futurist Michel Godet began developing scenarios for public institutions and companies in the mid-1970s, contributing to the emergence of the “La Prospective School” (Varum and Melo, 2010). Beyond its origins in military and public policy contexts, Barnett et al. (2025) note that scenario building has been widely employed as a strategic tool for reflecting on potential responses to uncertain future events. They further observe that the method has developed a long research tradition across economics, policy research, and emerging technology studies, to the extent that it has given rise to dedicated academic journals such as *Futures* and the *Journal of Forecasting*. Notably, the method was not originally created by academics, and its adoption has been widespread outside of academia; as Barnett et al. (2025) highlight, drawing on Varum and Melo (2010), scenario building is being used in corporate and industrial settings. The prominence of scenario building as a method is further evidenced by Popper's (2008) mapping of 886 foresight studies conducted across Europe, the Americas, Asia, and Australia, in which scenario building is identified as one of only three methods, alongside literature review and expert panels, that qualify as “widely used” rather than merely “commonly used” or “less frequently used.” He furthermore defines scenario building as “a method

that involves the construction and use of more or less systematic and internally consistent visions of plausible future states of affairs" (p. 88) and explicitly distinguishes this method from prediction or forecasting.

This distinction is important as early contributions to Futures Studies did not explicitly distinguish among its core components, and the terms *forecasting*, *foresight*, and *anticipation* "were used equivalently" (Cuhls, 2003, cited in Poli, 2019, p. 577), resulting in persistent conceptual ambiguity in both academic and practitioner contexts. In an effort to clarify Futures Studies terminology, philosopher Roberto Poli suggests that *forecasting* "deals with data extrapolation," *foresight* with "the visualization of possible futures," and *anticipation* with "their translation into action" (Poli, 2022, p. 577). Scenario building fits best within the domain of foresight, and by extension anticipation, because it is designed to explore futures whose trajectories remain open rather than to extrapolate from existing trends. In doing so, it enables the visualisation of a broad range of (highly) contrasted plausible futures, which can then guide open-up public debate or decision-making in contexts where there are uncertainties, such as the case of the joint ethical, social, and economic implications of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and data flows, as well as the potential evolution of regulatory frameworks and compliance mechanisms in the EU. As mentioned earlier, scenario building encompasses a range of formats, from expert-led approaches to participatory methods that actively engage diverse stakeholders in the construction of futures.

According to Sabol and Delina (2004), scenario building is "based on the idea that while strategic plans guide an organisation to where it wants to go, it is important to ask where the world is going. Without this knowledge, the best-laid plans may be completely thrown off course by events seemingly outside of the control of the organisation" (943). Here, a scenario is understood as an interpretation of the present, a representative image of the future, and an internally consistent story about the path leading from the present to the future (Sabol and Delina, 2004). Exploratory scenarios are constructed by identifying and examining key drivers of change and critical uncertainties that shape a given operating environment, spanning technological, environmental, social, economic, and political dimensions across local, national, and global scales, with the aim of rendering more visible the ways in which these forces may interact and shape future conditions (Sabol and Delina, 2004). Unlike methods such as the Delphi technique, which typically seek for convergence of expert opinions toward a single most probable outcome, scenario building is structured to generate multiple futures images through collaborative discussion, imagination, and visioning (Armanto, 2024). Since the objective of exploring plausible futures of AI, data flows, and their governance in the European Union spans a wide range of deeply uncertain and complex technical, regulatory, and socio-ethical issues, a method capable of accommodating multiple plausible futures rather than converging on a single projected outcome is required. It is precisely this capacity to hold open a plurality of futures, rather than converging on a single prediction, that makes scenario building a format particularly well-suited to anticipatory ethical inquiry in these domains which are characterised by deep uncertainty.

In Section 1.3, an overview of additional benefits but also limitations of scenario building are provided yet following a description of the typical process of scenario building. Prior to this though, it is important to furthermore make the distinction between *exploratory* scenarios and *normative* scenarios: Explorative scenarios address the question "what can happen?" by exploring possible futures from a variety of perspectives over a longer time horizon, allowing for profound structural changes and often starting from the future rather than the present (Börjeson et al., 2006). Normative scenarios, on the other hand, address questions such as, "How can a specific target be reached?" and "What should happen?" by starting from explicitly normative goals and working out how those objectives could be realised.

For the purposes of this study, exploratory scenarios are more appropriate than normative ones. Because the present exercise seeks to open up the full range of plausible futures of AI, data flows, and their governance rather than to pave a path toward a predetermined goal, the exploratory mode better serves the anticipatory and ethical aims of the broader HARNESS project. For the purposes of this study, exploratory scenarios are preferable to normative ones. As Glenn (2009) explains, any exercise oriented toward a single desired future "draws participants away from the [exploratory] scenario mindset and analysis," (p. 12) and precludes the analysis of a plurality of possible futures by constructing a single scenario with a predetermined end goal. Glenn also adds that, because the writer's mental model of cause and effect is subtly transferred to the reader and unconsciously accepted, a normative scenario with a predetermined goal may undeliberate impose the author's assumptions about what *should* happen, instead of *might*. Indeed, Glenn notes that normative scenarios are constructed precisely to organise developments around chosen norms and may even "become self-fulfilling to some degree" (p. 4), which makes them unsuitable for the broader HARNESS project, where the aim is to interrogate the very uncertainty that surrounds AI and data flows in the EU, than steer toward a fixed outcome.

1.2 Scenario Building Components

Drawing on the Futures Studies literature (Armanto, 2024; Börjeson et al., 2006; Glenn & The Futures Group International, 2009; Hiltunen, 2008; Poli, 2022; Sabol & Delina, 2004; Saghai, 2026), it is possible to outline the steps of a typical scenario building process (Saghai, 2026):

Step 1: Define the focal issue and the purpose of the exercise

Step 2: Set scope and time horizon (geographic scope, sector, actors, time horizon typically 5-30+ years)

Step 3: Identify driving forces of structural changes

Step 4: Distinguish predetermined elements and trends from critical uncertainties and weak signals, then rank critical uncertainties (impact and degree of uncertainty)

Step 5: Determine extreme behaviours of highest drivers of uncertainty (low, high values/states)

Step 6: Construct a matrix combining critical uncertainties

Step 7: Optional: reduce combination to 3-7 scenarios

Step 8: Create scenario narratives (state-of-affairs and pathways)

Step 9: Check narratives for internal consistency and plausibility and (optionally) quantify scenarios

Step 10: Discuss implications (e.g., policy stress-testing, possible actions)

Let us comment on the most extensive of these steps:

Step 3. Identify driving forces of structural changes

This step identifies potential structural changes (also referred to as "drivers of change" or "driving forces") within the system under analysis. A structural change is any significant shift in the system's components, in the interactions between those components, or in how the system relates to its broader environment. Whether a given change qualifies as "structural" depends on its scale and the extent to which it meaningfully affects the context under inquiry. To generate a comprehensive list of potential structural changes, brainstorming sessions or focus groups are typically used at this stage.

It is also worth noting that in addition to identifying structural changes, this stage can be used to scan for weak signals. First introduced by Ansoff (1975) and later developed within Futures Studies, weak signals are early indications of emerging issues or factors of change whose future significance is uncertain but potentially substantial (cited in Hiltunen, 2008). Unlike established drivers of change, which are already visible and well evidenced, weak signals often remain at the margins of attention and are easily overlooked as noise. Their value lies in broadening the range of possibilities considered before scenarios are developed. Examples of structural changes and weak signals can be found in Section 2. For each structural change identified, the next step, is to determine the assumptions on which it depends. An assumption is a claim about some feature of the system's structure or behaviour that must hold true for the structural change to occur. Each structural change typically rests on several assumptions, the validity of which is often uncertain.

Step 4: Distinguish predetermined elements and trends from critical uncertainties and weak signals, then rank critical uncertainties (impact and degree of uncertainty)

This step requires sorting each driving force into several categories. In particular, assumptions considered reasonably certain are classified as *predetermined* and are incorporated into every scenario. Those whose validity remains in doubt are classified as *uncertain* and are used to identify the key structural uncertainties that scenarios must address. Each critical uncertainty is assessed according to its degree of uncertainty and impact, sorting them into *high-impact* and *low-impact* and high-uncertainty and low-uncertainty groups. Drivers of change with high impact and high uncertainty together with the predetermined elements, form the foundation of the scenarios.

Step 6: Construct a matrix combining critical uncertainties

A scenario matrix is constructed by combining drivers of critical uncertainties and their values. For n drivers with k possible values/states each, the total number of possible combinations is k^n .

Thus, two driving forces with two values each yield four possible scenarios; three driving forces with two values each yield eight, and so on. In the simplest and most widely used form, the 2x2 method, two critical drivers are crossed to produce four contrasting scenarios:

2x2 Scenario Table

Driver B	B1	B2
Driver A		
A1	Scenario 1	Scenario 2
A2	Scenario 3	Scenario 4

Step 7: Optional: reduce combination to 3-7 scenarios

If the scenario space is larger than four possibilities, all combinations must be identified. For instance, with three drivers with two values each, the scenario space has eight possibilities:

	Driver A		Driver B		Driver C	
Scenarios	A1	A2	B1	B2	C1	C2
1	X		X		X	
2	X		X			X
3	X			X	X	
4	X			X		X
5		X	X		X	
6		X	X			X
7		X		X	X	
8		X		X		X

From the full scenario space, a subset is then selected and then expanded into actual narratives. Rather than developing every mathematically possible combination, a representative set is chosen to capture the widest and most contrasting range of plausible futures, while some combinations may be excluded as implausible or internally inconsistent. This can be done either through an informal workshop deliberation (pairwise compatibility judgments are made to identify incompatible combinations) or formally through morphological analysis (transparent and systematic elimination of incompatible combinations in cross-consistency matrix). Once inconsistent combinations are eliminated, the remaining combinations are clustered into families based on shared characteristics, with one representative scenario selected from each.

1.3 Benefits and Limits of Scenario Building

Prior to the development of any scenario building workshop, whether it is exploratory or normative, a set of practical and intellectual factors shapes its design, thereby determining its advantages and limitations. The primary and most salient factor is the resources available to the organizers. Time constitutes the main constraint, as scenario work may require days to weeks or months for preparation, facilitation, and follow-ups. Thus, a workshop confined to a single afternoon differs from one supported by an extended year-long research programme and a larger team. Material and financial resources are also significant, as they determine the number of participants who can be convened, whether specialists can be engaged, the extent of outreach, and the complexity of the outputs. Closely associated with this is the expertise and institutional context of the researchers conducting the exercise. This dimension is partly a function of resources as well-funded institutions with futures studies expert teams tend to possess greater experience and enhanced capacity to engage relevant stakeholders. However, expertise and methodological preferences do not reduce neatly to budgetary considerations. Researchers and institutions may have their own methodological preferences and theoretical commitments. Consequently, it is more appropriate to treat “scenario building” as a method that pertains to a broad family of methods, whose advantages and limitations are contingent to contextual circumstances, rather than as a uniform technique.

For these reasons, the strengths and weaknesses outlined below do not reflect any single, definitive method but are rather more generic, and result from our initial study phase, which encompassed the review of a broad range of scholarly and grey literature on futures studies to familiarise ourselves with the field. This literature spans topics from "The future as a public good: Decolonising the future through anticipatory participatory action research" (e.g., Bourgeois et al., 2024) to explicit workshop guidelines (e.g., van Asselt et al., 2010), as well as other futures-related publications from international organizations (e.g., World Bank) and the corporate sector (e.g., Deloitte). These strengths and weaknesses capture tendencies most likely to recur across the broader family of scenario-building approaches rather than the features of an idealized design.

Benefits:

- **Holds open a plurality of plausible futures rather than converging on a single predicted outcome:** by distributing attention to several internally consistent futures instead of analysis to one anticipated future, scenario building reduces the risk that ethical or policy assessments are based on a future that turns out to be implausible. This also resists the tendency of dominant narratives to foreclose alternative futures that other actors, including marginalised groups, might otherwise envision for themselves (Bourgeois et al., 2024).
- **Translates complex, long-term uncertainty into concrete, accessible narratives:** because scenarios take the form of stories rather than checklists, technical assessments, or abstract probability ranges, they make the reasoning behind anticipation easier to grasp and to debate for non-specialist audiences, e.g., policymakers and the public, and make abstract developments easier to engage with by presenting them as lived, concrete situations.
- **Surfaces tacit assumptions and creates space for dialogue across perspectives:** the process of constructing scenarios tends to bring to light normative commitments and assumptions that participants hold but had not previously articulated and can structure productive

exchange between actors who would not otherwise engage directly, whether specialists from different disciplines or affected communities and the institutions that govern them.

- **Functions as a stress-testing tool after construction** once built, a scenario set is not only a descriptive output but a tool that can be used afterward to test the robustness of existing or proposed policies, strategies, or institutional designs against a range of plausible futures, surfacing vulnerabilities that a single forecast would not reveal.

Challenges:

- **Outputs are sensitive to who constructs them and which drivers are selected:** regardless of whether the format is expert-led or participatory, the range of futures considered is bounded by the expertise, disciplinary background, and imagination of those constructing the scenarios, creating a risk of blind spots that is not eliminated simply by choosing one format over another.
- **May reinforce, rather than challenge, dominant assumptions about the future:** the resulting scenarios can end up extending current trends and existing power structures, limiting how transformative or inclusive the exercise turns out to be (depending on the design).
- **Scenarios can become outdated:** in fast-moving domains, a scenario set risks becoming outdated as real-world developments unfold, and because scenarios are not predictions, there is no straightforward way to assess their accuracy until well after the fact, if at all.
- **Resource and time intensive relative to more direct/systematic anticipatory methods:** constructing a defensible scenario set typically requires multiple workshops, drafting, and revision cycles, demanding more sustained effort than a single literature review or expert panel, which can be a constraining factor for smaller or time-limited projects.

2 RAPID LITERATURE REVIEW

This section presents the main findings from a rapid review conducted as a preparatory step aimed at informing design choices for the HARNESS scenario-building study, which will be presented in the next version of this deliverable.

2.1 Literature Search Strategy

The literature search followed a two-tier strategy: Tier 1 covered peer-reviewed literature via Scopus (primary data) and Web of Science (cross-checking data), while Tier 2 covered grey literature, which was essential as major scenario exercises are frequently published outside academic journals.

For the Tier 1 search of peer-reviewed literature, we consulted the databases SCOPUS and Web of Science. Table 1 outlines our search terms and results. We screened the results using Covidence. We excluded articles published before 2023, since ChatGPT was released in November 2022 and started an increased research interest into AI. We also excluded studies that were not written in English and document types that are not necessarily peer reviewed. During the screening process, we excluded results that conducted futures studies methods other than participatory scenario-building, such as AI-assisted scenario-building, sociotechnical imaginaries, and single roadmaps or scenarios. We included studies that created more than one scenario, which were not just presented but actively constructed in the study. Moreover, the studies must discuss drivers of change leading to the scenarios and the scenario-building was the main part of the paper. The scenarios also ought to be rather general on the future of AI rather than very specific on one domain, such as healthcare.

Table 1

Databases	Search terms	Filters	Results
SCOPUS	TITLE-ABS-KEY ((scenario* OR "futures studies" OR "foresight" OR "Delphi") AND ("artificial intelligence" OR "AI" OR "data flow*") AND ("European Union" OR "EU " OR "Europe" OR "GDPR" OR "AI Act")) AND PUBYEAR > 2021 AND PUBYEAR < 2027 AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (EXCLUDE (DOCTYPE , "no") OR EXCLUDE (DOCTYPE , "le") OR EXCLUDE (DOCTYPE , "ed") OR EXCLUDE (DOCTYPE , "dp") OR EXCLUDE (DOCTYPE , "cr") OR EXCLUDE (DOCTYPE , "re"))	None	446
Web of Science	TS=((scenario* OR "futures studies" OR "foresight" OR "Delphi") AND ("artificial intelligence" OR " AI " OR "data flow*")) AND ("European Union" OR "EU" OR "Europe" OR "GDPR" OR "AI Act")) AND PY=(2023-2026) AND LA=(English)	Exclude document type: Data set, meeting, review article, dissertation, awarded grant, abstract, patent, reference material, editorial material, clinical trial, data paper, letter	428

This first search only yielded one relevant study, which did not fulfil the requirement of generalness, but its focus on the labour market was rather broad, so we decided to include it. To improve our yield of studies, we made the search terms more general, by excluding the EU-related search terms. However, the high number of results were unmanageable, since the term “scenario” is also used in abstracts of highly unrelated papers. Thus, we changed the search term to synonyms of “scenario building,” as can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2

Databases	Search terms	Filters	Results
SCOPUS	TITLE-ABS-KEY(("scenario building*" OR "scenario planning" OR "scenario construct" OR "futures studies" OR "foresight" OR "Delphi") AND ("artificial intelligence" OR "AI" OR "data flow*") AND ("governance" OR "regulation" OR "regulatory framework*" OR "data governance" OR "digital governance")) AND (EXCLUDE (DOCTYPE,"sh") OR EXCLUDE (DOCTYPE,"cr") OR EXCLUDE (DOCTYPE,"ed") OR EXCLUDE (DOCTYPE,"no") OR EXCLUDE (DOCTYPE,"re")) AND PUBYEAR > 2023 AND PUBYEAR < 2026	None	187
Web of Science	TS= (("scenario building*" OR "scenario planning" OR "scenario construct" OR "futures studies" OR "foresight" OR "Delphi") AND ("artificial intelligence" OR "AI" OR "data flow*") AND (governance OR regulation OR "regulatory framework*" OR "data governance" OR "digital governance")) AND PY=(2023-2026) AND LA=(English)	Exclude document type: Data set, dissertation, review article, meeting, editorial material, patent, report, data study, news	150

We also screened these results in Covidence. It yielded 2 more relevant studies which we thought sufficient due to the expansive grey literature results in Tier 2.

For Tier 2 we searched EUR-Lex/EU Publications Office, the JRC publications portal, OECD iLibrary, RAND Europe, and World Economic Forum reports. Two strings were run and merged over: title, abstract, and keywords from 2023 onward: a core string combining scenario/foresight, AI, and governance terms, and a European-focus variant to capture EU-relevant comparative studies. Records were then screened in two steps within a shared spreadsheet, followed by an abstract-level inclusion check with certain requirements, including at least two distinct constructed scenarios, explicit discussion of drivers of change or uncertainties, scenario work as the primary contribution, and sufficiently general focus rather than domain-specific. The number of hits, exclusions, and inclusions was also recorded at each step (Table 3).

Table 3

Databases	Search terms	Filters	Results
Publications Office of the European Union	"futures studies" OR "foresight" OR "Delphi" (>2022)	None	112
JRC (Joint Research Centre) Publications Portal	"futures studies" OR "foresight" OR "Delphi" (2020-2029); "scenario" AND "foresight" (2020-2029)	None	282
OECD Publications	"Scenario" (2023-2026); "foresight" (2023-2026); "Delphi" (2023-2026); "artificial intelligence" (2023-2026); "anticipatory" (2023-2026)	None	527
RAND	"scenario" (2023-2026); "futures" AND "artificial" (2023-2026) [Content type: Research, Research Summary, Article, Project]	None	327
WEF	Only (<2022)	None	505

This targeted approach was better suited to our study than a full systematic review because the expected corpus was small and could be screened by two people in a short timeframe, whereas a full systematic review would have demanded considerably more resources without necessarily improving coverage for such a focused topic. The two-tier design also allowed us to capture grey literature that a strictly journal-based systematic search would have missed. Finally, studies found for the March 24th draft of this report were re-checked against these criteria, and those not qualifying as scenario studies but still informative on drivers of change were relocated to 2.5 Other studies. The total fifteen relevant studies we found are organised in the following sections. First, we present the extensive grey literature (11 studies), then the peer-reviewed academic literature (4 studies). The studies not selected through the literature search but found previously are included in the section afterwards. Finally, we synthesise and discuss these findings, paying special attention to trends and constants to inform our own scenarios, but also weaknesses that we aim to improve in our own scenario-building.

2.2 Grey Literature Exploratory Scenario Studies

This section concentrates exploratory scenario studies in the grey literature from which a standardised set of information was extracted for each study to facilitate comparison:

Scenario study parameters	
Focal issue	
Goal of exercise	
Methodology	
Time-horizon	
Geographical scope of the study	
Drivers of change/critical uncertainties	
Number of scenarios	
Stakeholders involvement	

The studies in this section are sorted alphabetically. We chose this order to enable fast and intuitive navigation and to mirror the formal bibliography. Table 4 gives an overview of the studies in this section.

Table 4

	Authors	Focus	Publication Date	Time horizon	No. of scenarios
1	Chessen & Chowdhury	Conceptualisation of ‘pivots’ of AGI futures to structure policy discussion, governance, and social implications	2025	Long-term	No specific scenarios; 6 ‘pivots’ of events in possible AGI futures
2	Cleaveland et al.	The future of cybersecurity and digital security governance across regions by 2030, including role of AI	2023	2030	4 scenarios used in workshop, but not described in the report
3	Crotta et al.	How geoeconomics and technology adoption shape the global economy by 2030	2025	2030	4 scenarios
4	GovUK	The future development of Frontier AI, with a focus on implications for the UK	2024	2030	5 scenarios
5	Hobbs et al.	AI’s evolution by 2030 and its implications for policy, innovation, and risk	2026	2030	4 scenarios
6	Mattioli & Malatras	Cybersecurity threats by 2030, focusing on socio-political dynamics and market structures	2024	2030	5 scenarios
7	Pasimeni & Dotti	How demographic change will reshape the EU’s Research and Innovation	2025	2050	4 scenarios
8	Özcan et al.	The future of AI and its impact on economic growth, geopolitics, social contract, security, and human agency	2025	2032	5 scenarios
9	Pavel et al.	Geopolitical implications of AGI and how AGI can alter the balance of power for the US, with a very heavy focus on the US	2025	Long-term	8 scenarios
10	Sytsma	Economic growth implications of AI systems	2025	2045	2 scenarios
11	Vesnic-Alujević et al.	The global standing and geopolitical role of the EU in 2040	2023	2040	4 scenarios

Report 1: Pivots and pathways on the road to artificial general intelligence futures

Authors: Chessen, M., & Chowdhury, S.

Date: 2025

Institution: RAND Corporation

The report presents a conceptualisation and classification of AGI futures through a shared framework that the authors call “pivots.” They can be used to structure policy discussions about AGI. They develop a conceptual framework and demonstrate how to use it to build scenarios by describing how different combinations of pivots can affect factors such as human flourishing or democracy. They formulate the pivots by synthesizing literature on AGI governance, AI safety, geopolitics, and foresight. The results are six binary pivots that can be combined to build multiple AGI futures. The pivots are:

1. *Centralization of ownership:* centralised vs. decentralized
2. *Governance primacy:* dominantly public or private interests
3. *Alignment level:* aligned or misaligned with societal values
4. *Take-off speed:* gradual vs. rapid
5. *Human-AGI relationship:* AGI complements or replaces humans
6. *AGI volition:* independent actor vs. controlled tool

Focal issue	Conceptualization and classification of possible artificial general intelligence (AGI) futures through a shared framework of “pivots” that structure policy discussions about AGI trajectories, governance, and societal implications.
Goal of exercise	To provide policymakers and AI stakeholders with a common vocabulary and analytical framework for discussing AGI futures, clarifying assumptions, generating scenarios, and testing policy robustness across alternative AGI pathways.
Methodology	Conceptual scenario-framework development and qualitative futures analysis. The study synthesizes literature on AGI governance, AI safety, geopolitics, and foresight to develop six “pivots” (classification axes) describing alternative AGI futures. It is primarily a typological and analytical framework rather than a formal scenario exercise. The study develops six binary pivots (axes) that can be combined into multiple AGI futures: centralization of ownership, governance primacy, alignment level, take-off speed, human–AGI relationship, and AGI volition.
Time-horizon	Long-term AGI futures
Geographical scope	Global
Drivers of change/critical uncertainties	Centralization of ownership: centralised vs. decentralized Governance primacy: dominantly public or private interests Alignment level: aligned or misaligned with societal values Take-off speed: gradual vs. rapid

	Human-AGI relationship: AGI complements or replaces humans AGI volition: independent actor vs. controlled tool
Number of scenarios	No scenarios, just 6 pivots described
Stakeholder involvement	The paper was informed by discussions and reviews involving RAND researchers and AI policy experts

Report 2: Report Cybersecurity futures 2030: New foundations

Authors: Cleaveland, A., Cohn, A., Nagamine, M., Thomas, D., Rimsky Vernon, A., Bouckaert, J., & Joshi, A.

Date: 2023

Institutions: World Economic Forum; UC Berkeley Centre for Long-Term Cybersecurity; CNA Institute for Public Research

This paper discusses the future of cybersecurity and digital security governance in 2030, with focus on the role of AI, geopolitics, trust, and data privacy. This report presents the findings of workshops conducted worldwide by the UC Berkeley Centre for Long-term Cybersecurity (CLTC), the World Economic Forum, and CNA. The workshops took place in UAE, USA, Rwanda, India, Singapore, and EU/UK. They consisted of 4 pre-designed scenarios used as discussion prompts. The results of the workshop are synthesised in the report. The main results were that the accelerated technology development requiring societies to completely reorient their approach to digital security. Trust will be a key goal of cybersecurity efforts. Moreover, education on cybersecurity needs to be improved.

Focal issue	The future of cybersecurity and digital security governance across regions by 2030, including the roles of AI, geopolitics, trust, and data privacy
Goal of exercise	To inform cybersecurity strategic planning for governments, industry, academia and civil society globally; to elicit diverse regional perspectives on shared digital security challenges and trade-offs
Methodology	Scenario-based workshop facilitation: 4 pre-designed scenarios (developed by CLTC between Jan–Apr 2023) used as discussion prompts in 6 workshops across international locations; qualitative synthesis of workshop outputs. The scenarios themselves are referenced but not reproduced here (this report presents only the workshop findings)
Time-horizon	2030 (5–7 years from the writing date of 2023)
Geographical scope	Global, with explicit regional differentiation: UAE, USA, Rwanda, India, Singapore, and Europe/UK
Drivers of change/critical uncertainties	Pace and scale of digitalization; AI and automation; quantum computing and IoT; US-China geopolitical rivalry; digital sovereignty vs. interoperability; mis/dis/mal-information (MDM); cybersecurity talent supply; data privacy and data governance; sustainability and climate-tech entanglement; trust in institutions
Number of scenarios	4 (designed by CLTC; used as workshop stimuli but not described in this report)
Stakeholder involvement	Workshops in 6 locations with participants from government, business, civil society, and academia; corporate partners included Fortinet, Meta, Okta, and Repsol

Report 3: Four futures for the new economy: Geoeconomics and technology in 2030

Authors: Crotta, F., Betti, F., Di Battista, A., Elsner, M., Karunska, K., & Zahidi, S.

Date: 2025

Institution: World Economic Forum

This report discusses the global economy in 2030 will be shaped by geoeconomics and technology adoption. The authors provide four scenarios from a 2x2 matrix based on the two critical uncertainties of (1) stable vs. volatile geopolitical context and (2) slow vs. fast technology adoption. While the authors explore the scenarios and potential economic impacts in depth, the method is not explained as thoroughly. It consists of a survey of chief strategy officers' conceptions on which trends shape their business strategies the most. The survey's results led to vectors of geopolitical context and technology adoption. Again, the authors do not aim to predict the most likely future but present the four futures to enable businesses to plan strategy for multiple future possibilities and navigate uncertainty. The futures are:

1. *Digitalized Order* (stable & rapid): The US and China trade wars have not escalated, the rivalry is predictable and does not lead to unrest. Global military spending has plateaued. Rapid commercialisation of AI technologies diffuses technologies beyond companies and borders. Moreover, digital interoperability is at a high, altogether leading to renewed stability. However, inequality remains, such as a polarised labour market.
2. *Cautious Stability* (stable & slow): The global order is predictable and stable. Major conflicts have died down, yet the global economy is not picking up. The slower adoption of technology limits technology to a few sectors, as most businesses have skill gaps and no sufficient infrastructure to support emerging technologies. Since AI is commercialised, yet not readily picked up, the AI bubble bursts and AI lose stock value, which also leads to less investment and innovation happening in the field of AI. Replacement of human labour is less than expected, since AI is adopted rather slowly. However, less adoption of cutting-edge technologies limits the potential for developing renewable energy technologies and transforming the global energy systems.
3. *Tech-based Survival* (volatile & rapid): The environment for businesses in this volatile and rapid scenario is filled with opportunities, yet also high-risk. Countries and their allies diffuse and share their technologies, yet between other nations conflicts and fragmentation are increasing. The global technology race has increased, where different hubs are competing for increasing skilled workers and innovation. Global trade is fragmented and labour markets' technology adoption increases, so that workers need to transition to new digital skills.
4. *Geotech Spheres* (volatile & slow): The rivalry between the US and China has escalated to lead to proxy conflicts, cyber threats and a fractured global network, inhibiting a free flow of capital, knowledge, data, and talent. The access to key technologies, such as AI, is limited and weaponised by governments, focused on military development. Since also the trust in technology by the public has decreased, technology adoption is slow. Only a low number of tech companies have access to AI, excluding smaller companies. As a result, large companies

get richer, and smaller ones lose profit. Domestically, nations face polarisation, since investment into the military requires cuts of social spending.

Focal issue	How the interaction between geoeconomics and technology adoption will shape the global economy by 2030. There is a strong focus on the implications for businesses.
Goal of exercise	To provide four scenarios that help businesses stress-test assumptions, anticipate risks, and design resilient strategies.
Methodology	2x2 scenario matrix based on two critical uncertainties: (1) geopolitical context (stable vs. volatile), (2) technology adoption (slow vs. fast).
Time-horizon	2030
Geographical scope	Global
Drivers of change/critical uncertainties	Main: Geopolitical stability vs. volatility Pace and breadth of technology adoption Trade and investment flows Labour market transformation Energy system volatility Domestic political polarization Supply chain resilience AI commercialization and regulation
Number of scenarios	4 scenarios
Stakeholder involvement	World Economic Forum Chief Strategy Officers Community; industry experts; Global Foresight Network; cross-sector workshops.

Report 4: AI 2030 scenarios

Date: 2024

Institution: UK Government Office for Science, Department for Science, Innovation and Technology

This report was published by the UK government Office for Science on how advanced so-called Frontier AI may develop and affect the world by 2030. The goal was to help policymakers understand the possible development and test their strategies against a number of possible future outcomes. Using a methodology combining morphological analysis with participatory scenario-planning workshops, the authors built five scenarios from five critical uncertainties: AI capability, ownership and access, safety, level of use, and geopolitical context. The five scenarios are:

1. *Unpredictable Advanced AI:* Developers manage a breakthrough in autonomous AI agents. The release of these agents catches regulators off guard, which enables scientific breakthroughs and malicious harm within weeks. Safety regulations lag behind AI's capabilities, leaving society exposed to unpredictable consequences.
2. *AI Disrupts Workforce:* AI systems become highly capable, yet more narrow than in scenario 1. They are used in robotics and autonomous vehicles and deployed rapidly, disrupting the workforce. While these AI systems are safer than the ones from scenario 1, they still trigger increased unemployment and rising social inequality.
3. *AI 'Wild West':* The AI market is diverse, including more moderately capable and highly capable systems from multiple global actors. Disinformation, fraud, deepfakes, and espionage increase. Authorities have problems regulating the dispersed availability of AI systems and an international consensus on a common AI governance is lacking.
4. *Advanced AI on a Knife Edge:* Although a major tech company launches an AGI system with remarkable capabilities, safety infrastructure struggles to understand its full capabilities. The AGI brings with it economic benefits, yet it can also cause harm since its full capabilities and its full understanding and intelligence is unknown.
5. *AI Disappoints:* AI progress stalls, not reaching the high expectations of many. Due to lacking accuracy, limited data, and barriers to implementation, investors turn their backs to AI. Society grows indifferent to AI after the hype dies down. Safety researchers keep up their work, since targeted AI misuse still exists.

Focal issue	The future development of Frontier AI (most capable and general AI models), with a focus on risks, opportunities, and policy implications for the UK up to the year 2030
Goal of exercise	To help policymakers, industry, and society understand and explore uncertainties of AI development
Methodology	The authors combined a qualitative scenario-building workshop with a general morphological analysis to understand the interactions between variables. They first identified critical uncertainties, narrowed them down to less using the morphological analysis, and decided on 5 final scenarios with uncertainties through expert voting.
Time-horizon	2030

Geographical scope of the study	Primary focus on the UK, while the scenarios also consider global geopolitics
Drivers of change/critical uncertainties	5 main critical uncertainties, each with sub-uncertainties <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Capability 2. Ownership, access, and constraints 3. Safety 4. Level and distribution of use 5. Geopolitical context
Number of scenarios	5 scenarios, namely <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Unpredictable advanced AI 2. AI disrupts the workforce 3. AI 'Wild West' 4. Advanced AI on a knife edge 5. AI disappoints
Stakeholders' involvement	The report had expert involvement from academia, industry, and government departments. Moreover, they included participants from the general public to take part in the workshops

Report 5: Exploring possible AI trajectories through 2030

Authors: Hobbs, H., Docherty, D., Aranda, L., Perset, K., Sugimoto, K., & Kierzenkowski, R.

Date: 2026

Institution: OECD Publishing

This paper builds a set of four broad scenario classes for AI through 2030: Progress Stalls, Progress Slows, Progress Continues, and Progress Accelerates. The authors use an inductive approach, combining many factors, trends, expert interviews, and evidence on AI capability progress into scenario storylines rather than reducing the analysis to a two-driver matrix. Notably, the study's inclusion of social acceptance and ethical considerations as a structural factor shaping AI trajectories is distinctive, most technical foresight exercises treat these as secondary constraints rather than as genuine uncertainties capable of redirecting the pace and direction of AI development altogether. The study's method combines a literature review, expert interviews and review, trend analysis, horizon scanning, driver mapping, technology road mapping, and trend extrapolation using OECD beta AI Capability Indicators. The scenario logic is built around nine capability areas: language, social interaction, problem solving, creativity, metacognition and critical thinking, knowledge /learning /memory, vision, physical manipulation, and robotic intelligence. The scenarios are not treated as predictions, and the paper assigns no probabilities to them.

- *In Progress Stalls*, frontier AI capabilities plateau soon after 2025, with later systems remaining similar to 2025 models but refined for usability and application integration. AI remains strong at structured language tasks and some reasoning, but still depends heavily on human prompting, review, and contextual input, while memory, agency, real-world problem solving, physical tasks, and social interaction remain weak. The main drivers of this outcome are limits in scaling, weak returns from reasoning training, lack of major algorithmic breakthroughs, and falling investment or adoption.
- *In Progress Slows*, AI continues improving, but at a slower pace after 2025. Systems become very strong assistants for expert questions, structured reasoning, computer use, and limited agentic tasks, yet still struggle with continual learning, physical embodiment, and complex social interaction. This scenario reflects maturity in deep learning, higher costs, and bottlenecks in compute, data, and investment.
- *In Progress Continues*, rapid gains persist and AI systems can perform many professional digital tasks with high autonomy. They improve substantially in reasoning, memory, tool use, and robotic support, though real-world generalisation and complex social settings still lag.
- *In Progress Accelerates*, AI reaches human-equivalent performance across most or all cognitive capabilities, with seamless continual learning, strong autonomy, and advanced robotic and social capabilities. The paper highlights uncertainty over whether scaling, reasoning, and AI-assisted AI development will continue or hit limits.

Focal issue	How artificial intelligence (AI) may evolve over the next decade, with a focus on AI trajectories by 2030 and their implications for policy, innovation, and risk management, using the OECD’s beta AI Capability Indicators to map capability across nine dimensions (e.g., language, problem-solving, vision, robotics, and metacognition).
Goal of exercise	To improve understanding of plausible AI development paths towards 2030, support policy-making under uncertainty, and help governments and organisations design robust strategies that remain effective across a range of AI trajectories (stalled, slow, continuing, and accelerating progress).
Methodology	A scenario-based foresight approach built on expert-informed, non-probabilistic scenarios, using the OECD’s beta AI Capability Indicators to disaggregate progress across nine capability domains; the exercise also draws on trend analysis and expert workshops to ensure internally consistent storyline; the authors use scenario narratives constructed around varying degrees of AI progress and uncertainty, rather than a reduced matrix of two drivers.
Time-horizon	2030; the scenarios explore AI progress over roughly the next 5–10 years from the publication date (2026), with a clear 2030 focal year.
Geographical scope	Global, with a focus on OECD-member countries and major AI-developing economies, informing international policy coordination and standards-setting.
Drivers of change/critical uncertainties	Key drivers and uncertainties include: scaling of compute and data, algorithmic efficiency, power and energy constraints, data scarcity, regulatory and governance frameworks, social and ethical acceptance, and labour-market and skill-system responses; the report stresses high uncertainty about whether AI progress will stall, slow, continue, or accelerate by 2030.

Report 6: Foresight cybersecurity threats for 2030

Authors: Mattioli, R., & Malatras, A.

Date: 2024

Institution: European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA).

This report updates ENISA's earlier 2030 cybersecurity foresight by revisiting threats, trends, and scenarios through a structured exercise combining a real-time Delphi survey and an online workshop with experts. Its purpose is to reassess the 2022 threat landscape, identify new or rising trends, and refine the scenario space so that it better reflects how cybersecurity risks may evolve by 2030. The scenario space is built from the workshop's reinterpretation of the original ENISA scenarios and from expert comments on what should be strengthened, clarified, or added. The authors do not present the scenarios as forecasts; rather, they use them to test how different technological, political, legal, and environmental dynamics might interact under divergent futures.

The revised scenario set contains five named scenarios:

1. *Blockchain, Deepfakes, & Cybercrime in a Data-Rich Environment* describes a world where blockchain is widely used but not universally fit for purpose, while criminals exploit cryptocurrencies, the darknet, and strong encryption; deepfakes spread distrust, and AI-empowered infrastructure becomes vulnerable to manipulation and e-waste concerns.
2. *Eco-Friendly, Sustainable, and Interconnected Smart Cities (Non-State Actors)* focuses on water scarcity, climate pressure, smart-city governance, and the rising political influence of non-state actors, including tech giants and wealthy individuals, in shaping infrastructure and local governance.
3. *More Data, Less Control* examines automated, data-driven decision-making, ethical risks, data breaches, trust erosion, and the tension between privacy, consent, and law-enforcement access in a heavily digitised environment.
4. *Sustainable Energy, Automated and Short-Term Workforce* explores decentralised energy systems, agricultural automation, short-term labour structures, outsourcing, and the cybersecurity implications of platformised work and dependency on software service providers.
5. *Legislation, Bias, Extinctions, & Global Threats* brings together internet fragmentation, digital sovereignty, climate-related infrastructure disruption, AI and data biases, and dependencies on space-based systems and sovereign LEO constellations.

Across the report, the main trends include the growing political power of non-state actors, cybersecurity in elections, data-intensive behavioural analysis, outsourced IT, satellite dependence, connected vehicles, digital energy consumption, and the increasing difficulty of controlling personal data.

Focal issue	Emerging cybersecurity threats projected for the year 2030, with a focus on how evolving technologies, socio-political dynamics, and market structures may reshape the EU's cyber-threat landscape (e.g., supply-chain compromises, AI-driven attacks, disinformation, hybrid threats, environmental-physical disruptions).
Goal of exercise	To review and update the 2030-oriented ENISA "Foresight Cybersecurity Threats" list, assess how threats and trends have evolved since 2022, and refine scenarios in order to inform EU-level policy, research, and operational preparedness for future cyber risks.
Methodology	A two-step foresight process: (1) Real-time Delphi survey with 24 cybersecurity experts assessing 21 threats by impact and likelihood; and (2) a thematic workshop using 4CF's "Stranger Futures" method to revisit trends and scenarios. The "Stranger Futures" method is a creative foresight technique that prompts participants to deliberately challenge and reframe their assumptions about the future by imagining unexpected or counterintuitive scenarios, essentially asking " <i>what if the opposite or something strange were true?</i> " It is designed to surface blind spots and hidden biases in conventional trend analysis, helping analysts avoid anchoring too heavily on familiar or comfortable futures. The overall approach is grounded in ENISA's own foresight methodology and PESTLE-type trend analysis.
Time-horizon	Explicitly forward-looking to 2030, with assessments of how threats and trends may evolve over roughly the next decade from the 2022 baseline.
Geographical scope	European Union-wide, addressing ENISA-member-state stakeholders, EU-level policymaking, and cross-border ICT dependencies and supply chains.
Drivers of change/critical uncertainties	Nine key trends identified as highly susceptible to change by 2030: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Political: increased power of non-state actors 2. Political: cybersecurity-related interference in elections 3. Economic: intensified behavioural data collection and analysis, especially in the private sector 4. Economic: growing reliance on outsourced IT services 5. Social: decision-making increasingly based on automated analysis of data 6. Technological: rising dependency on satellites as their numbers in space increase 7. Technological: vehicles becoming more connected to each other and the outside world, with less reliance on human operation 8. Environmental: increasing energy consumption of digital infrastructure 9. Legal: growing difficulty and desirability of controlling data about oneself, whether as an individual, company, or state

Report 7: The Demographic Turn: Actions Needed for Research, Innovation and Policy in Europe

Authors: Pasimeni P., & Dotti N.

Date: 2025

Institution: Publications Office of the European Union

This report examines how Europe's demographic shift toward an older, smaller, and more unevenly distributed population will reshape the Research and Innovation (RI) system by 2050. It identifies three main pressures: the shrinking talent pool, the fiscal squeeze caused by rising pension and healthcare costs, and the productivity paradox, meaning that Europe must raise output with fewer workers while avoiding social fragmentation. The study's scenario work is based on weak signals and PESTLE-scanned trends, then reduced to two critical uncertainties: the degree of automation in research and whether public or business actors dominate research provision.

The four scenarios are as follows:

1. **Corporate ascendancy** describes a future in which fiscal strain and weak regulation allow corporations to dominate RI, public universities decline, research becomes market-driven, and knowledge increasingly turns proprietary; the scenario also includes a two-tier education system and a cautious, human-led approach to technology after a major cyberattack.
2. **Inclusion and purpose** imagine a post-growth, socially equitable Europe with stronger investment in regional cohesion and ethical technology, but it is limited by digital fatigue among older citizens, declining trust in institutions, and slow scientific momentum.
3. **Splinters stratification** presents a fragmented global order shaped by a Splinternet, closed borders, and protective blocs; RI becomes more isolated, duplication rises, migration is restricted, and research agendas are shaped by public tenders, corporate control, and local information filters.
4. **Hybrid hubs** depict a resilient EU that combines distributed regional innovation campuses, human-AI collaboration, and strategic autonomy, balancing specialisation with coordinated investment.

Across the scenarios, the report highlights recurring trends and weak signals: ageing, shrinking youth cohorts, labour shortages, rising dependency ratios, digital fatigue, populist distrust, increased automation, geopolitical fracture, regional divergence, the silver economy, and the growing importance of AI and data governance. The report then translates these futures into four policy mandates: Protection, Adaptation, Cohesion, and Trust.

Focal issue	How demographic change (ageing populations, shrinking youth and workforce, migration shifts, slower growth) will reshape the EU's Research and Innovation (R&I) system up to 2050, including implications for talent, funding, productivity, and regional cohesion
Goal of exercise	To anticipate future stresses on Europe's R&I system from demographic change, develop scenario-based stress-tests for 2050, and propose concrete policy actions (mandates) that protect, adapt, cohere, and build trust in a future-proof R&I model.
Methodology	A Foresight-on-Demand process combining weak-signal and trend analysis (demographic, economic, technological) with scenario-building and "wind-tunnelling" (testing policy options against multiple futures); the process includes horizon scanning, stakeholder consultations, and expert workshops feeding into four scenario narratives (qualitatively framed futures) and four strategic mandate-based policy clusters (protection, adaptation, cohesion, trust) derived from trend interactions.
Time-horizon	2050; the analysis projects demographic and R&I-system dynamics over roughly the next 25–30 years from the publication date
Geographical scope	European Union-wide, with a focus on EU-level R&I governance, Horizon Europe, national and regional R&I systems, and cross-border demographic and labour-market dynamics
Drivers of change/critical uncertainties	Key drivers include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demographic: ageing, shrinking youth, declining workforce; • Economic: slower growth, fiscal pressure on public R&I budgets, rising productivity needs; • Social: shifting migration patterns, inequality, multigenerational workforce; • Technological: AI-driven automation in research, digital-age productivity tools; • Policy: varying national • ageing-response strategies, migration policies, R&I funding models, and public trust in science and innovation.
Number of scenarios	The report constructs four scenarios for Europe's R&I system by 2050 (e.g., corporate-dominated R&I, post-growth equity-oriented model, geopolitically fragmented system, and distributed "hybrid hub" regional-innovation network), each illustrating a different response to demographic pressures and policy choices.
Stakeholder involvement	Core stakeholder groups involved: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU and national R&I policymakers (EU-level governance, ERA- and Horizon-Europe-related actors). • Higher-education and research institutions, innovation agencies, and regional R&I stakeholders. • Foresight and social-science experts (via the Foresight-on-Demand consortium and 4CF).

Report 8: Advanced AI: Possible Futures

Authors: Özcan, B., Juijn, D., Graabak, J., & Bogerd, S.

Date: 2025

Institution: Centre for Future Generations

The report was made by the think tank Centre for Future Generations. It outlines five scenarios of the future of advanced AI from 2025-2032. Its goal is to inform policymakers on decision-making and help anticipate rapid technology development. As their methodology, the authors conducted desk research on suitable scenario development approaches and on drivers of change in advanced AI. They also consulted experts in feedback sessions to refine the scenarios. To build the scenarios the authors identified drivers of change as parameters, starting off with 25 parameters, and condensing them into 9 core parameters. From 512 scenarios from all parameter combinations, the authors decided on 10 main narratives, which were formed into scenarios with more expert feedback. These 10 scenarios were then further condensed and combined into 5. The scenarios are outlined on a year-by-year basis and offer two types of endings.

1. *Plateau:* The 'data wall' will lead to AI reaching its limits of progress. This means that smaller and locally run models become more popular opposed to large tech companies running large models. One of the two endings of the scenario posits a future where more useful and less spectacular AI has widespread access and stability, while the other ending sees a future where the open systems fuel cyberattacks and shatter trust.
2. *Big AI:* In this scenario AI becomes indispensable and integrated into every aspect of life. Due to deepfakes causing severe crises in society, open models are limited and closed, now limited to a few companies. AI continues to have proponents and critics. The scenario can end with constant digital growth, yet neglected ethics, or the total monopoly of a few firms on AI, making them immune to even government control.
3. *Diplomacy:* Due to AI's rapid capability increase, safety is put to the forefront, and companies need to hold back their advanced AI systems. Both governments and companies prioritise safety and monitoring. One ending pictures a few select firms holding monopoly on the now restricted AI systems. The other ending sees an increased rivalry between countries, such as the USA and China, keeping their systems secret and apart from each other and battling for approval of governments and trust and safety to deploy their systems.
4. *Arms Race:* In this scenario the US and China see AI as a strategic asset and invest strongly in it. They both deploy military AI-systems, and their AI-rivalry influences geopolitics. This scenario could spill over into an actual armed conflict or akin to a cold war scenario, and anxiety and mistrust simmer between nations.
5. *Take-off:* In this scenario AI accelerates exponentially, reaching the development of AI hiveminds. Humans take the backseat and are in oversight roles only, while AI takes the lead. One ending proposes a future where AI's super intelligence solves many problems, freeing society from economic burdens and offering space for reflection. The second ending sees a

dystopian future where AI is designed to serves its own interests and works against humanity.

Focal issue	Exploring the future of AI and how it could impact economic growth, geopolitics, the social contract, security, and human agency
Goal of exercise	To inform policymakers and help them anticipate and govern rapid technological change
Methodology	The methodology included desk research, scanning drivers of change, expert engagement, and scenario construction
Time-horizon	2032
Geographical scope of the study	Global
Drivers of change/critical uncertainties	The progress of AI's capabilities and the centralisation of control of advanced AI
Number of scenarios	Five scenarios, namely <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Plateau 2. Big AI 3. Diplomacy 4. Arms Race 5. Take-off
Stakeholders involvement	The study involved expert engagement from tech companies, universities and governance. The funding came from philanthropic sources related to the effective altruism movement.

Report 9: How Artificial General Intelligence Could Affect The Rise and Fall Of Nations: Visions for Potential AGI Futures

Authors: Pavel, B., Ke, I., Smith, G., Brown-Heidenreich, S., Sabbag, L., Acharya, A., & Mahmood, Y.

Date: 2025

Institution: RAND Corporation

This report treats the geopolitical implications of AGI and how it could alter the global balance of power. The authors constructed 8 long-term scenarios by using mixed-methods. Their method was inspired by RAND's assumption-based planning, in which the assumptions underlying a scenario are identified to understand weaknesses where the scenario could fail. Moreover, they conducted a literature review, 26 expert interviews, and exploratory scenario development. The scenarios are constructed on a 2x4 matrix with two main dimensions: centralised vs. decentralised AGI development and geopolitical outcomes (empowers U.S.; empowers adversaries; disempowers all; AGI halted).

1. *Multilateral Coalition of Democracies* (US empowered & decentralised): AGI systems are developed in the US, EU, China, and Japan. AGI is not particularly used in military offense technology, but also in defensive technologies. The US and its allies gain an advantage due to its tech companies and quick implementation of AGI in the military. They are equipped with tools to fit cyber threats. The US and its allies also restrict access to chips and hardware required to build AGI. This keeps the US as the AGI leader, where China and Russia fail to keep up.
2. *Cold War 2* (US adversaries & decentralised): The US and China are leaders in AI development and rival in being the leader. This leads to battling for infrastructure and strategic partnerships and increases geopolitical tensions. Both aim to increase AI development for economic gain. AGI is increasingly used in the military, which builds anxiety to a starting war. The two nations stay similar in the capabilities of their AGIs.
3. *The Wild Frontier* (US and adversaries disempowered & decentralised): Countries are unable to keep at bay the use and development of AGI, with required hardware being widely available and models are open-source. This leads to state and non-state actors using their own AGI systems, where states seek to use it for military use, while corporations use it for economic gain. Because of the widespread use, dangerous systems developed, without human oversight.
4. *The Corked Bottle* (development halted & decentralised): After an AI-incident triggers concern about AGI-development, the international community is mandated to limit AGI development. Also the US and China signed such a treaty. Nations stay suspicious if other nations develop AGI secretly to gain advantage. Thus, nations aim to monitor each other carefully. The geopolitical landscape remains unstable.
5. *The New '90s* (US empowered & centralised): The US is the leader in AGI development. The US government decides to control AI development and not share with other countries. While the US manages to more or less safely implement their AGI into their society, outside actors lack behind in development.

6. *Authoritarian Advantage* (US adversaries & centralised): AGI systems are developed and used in authoritarian regimes, since they manage to centrally control its use. China takes the lead in AGI development. The AI systems spread to other nations and encourage authoritarian states to use it for surveillance and other aims. The US faces internal conflict, and to avoid dependence on China, follows a protectionist foreign policy. This causes economic decline in the US.
7. *The AGI Coup* (US and adversaries disempowered & centralised): AI companies aim to be the first to reach AGI development, where the ones with a cautious approach fall behind. The safeguards fall through and with more and more AGI being implemented, it becomes impossible to remove its influence. AGI becomes a dominant geopolitical actor.
8. *Mushroom Cloud Computing* (development halted & centralised): This scenario outlines how nations that may fall behind in the AI race, might take radical actions, such as military attacks to stop their rivals' increasingly fast AGI development.

Focal issue	Geopolitical implications of artificial general intelligence (AGI); how AGI could alter the global balance of power for the US (there is a very strong focus on the consequences for the US).
Goal of exercise	To help policymakers think about the historic importance of AGI for geopolitics, broaden thinking about possible AGI futures, and provide plausible scenarios for policy preparation.
Methodology	Scenario analysis using a mixed-methods approach; inspired by RAND's assumption-based planning (ABP). "In ABP, assumptions underlying a particular scenario or plan are identified to understand the potential weaknesses or points of failure underlying a particular planned outcome, and signposts can be developed to monitor whether those assumptions are vulnerable to failing." Methods included literature review, exploratory scenario development, and 26 semistructured expert interviews. The framework used two analytical axes: degree of AGI centralization and geopolitical outcomes. Primarily a 2x4 scenario matrix/framework. Two main dimensions: (1) centralized vs decentralized AGI development; (2) four geopolitical outcomes (empowers U.S.; empowers adversaries; disempowers all; AGI halted). This produced eight scenarios
Time-horizon	Long-run / future-oriented AGI futures; no explicit fixed year horizon, although discussion references possible AGI emergence in coming decades and cites AI 2027-type forecasting literature.
Geographical scope	Global, with strong emphasis on the United States, China, allies, and international geopolitical order.
Drivers of change/critical uncertainties	Degree of AGI centralization and geopolitical outcomes.

<p>Number of scenarios</p>	<p>8 scenarios</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Table 1. Potential AGI Futures</p> <hr/> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="text-align: left; border-bottom: 1px solid black;">Situation</th> <th style="text-align: center; border-bottom: 1px solid black;">AGI Development Empowers the United States</th> <th style="text-align: center; border-bottom: 1px solid black;">AGI Development Empowers U.S. Adversaries</th> <th style="text-align: center; border-bottom: 1px solid black;">AGI Development Disempowers the United States and U.S. Adversaries</th> <th style="text-align: center; border-bottom: 1px solid black;">AGI Development Is Halted</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td style="border-right: 1px solid black;">Multiple actors tightly race to develop AGI (decentralized development)</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Scenario 1: Multilateral Coalition of Democracies Leads</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Scenario 2: Cold War 2</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Scenario 3: The Wild Frontier</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Scenario 4: The Corked Bottle</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="border-right: 1px solid black;">One actor leads AGI development (centralized development)</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Scenario 5: The New '90s: (U.S. Leadership)</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Scenario 6: Authoritarian Advantage (PRC Dominance)</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Scenario 7: The AGI Coup</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Scenario 8: Mushroom Cloud Computing (War)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p><small>SOURCE: Analysis of existing literature and interviewees' input. NOTE: PRC = People's Republic of China.</small></p>	Situation	AGI Development Empowers the United States	AGI Development Empowers U.S. Adversaries	AGI Development Disempowers the United States and U.S. Adversaries	AGI Development Is Halted	Multiple actors tightly race to develop AGI (decentralized development)	Scenario 1: Multilateral Coalition of Democracies Leads	Scenario 2: Cold War 2	Scenario 3: The Wild Frontier	Scenario 4: The Corked Bottle	One actor leads AGI development (centralized development)	Scenario 5: The New '90s: (U.S. Leadership)	Scenario 6: Authoritarian Advantage (PRC Dominance)	Scenario 7: The AGI Coup	Scenario 8: Mushroom Cloud Computing (War)
Situation	AGI Development Empowers the United States	AGI Development Empowers U.S. Adversaries	AGI Development Disempowers the United States and U.S. Adversaries	AGI Development Is Halted												
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<p>Stakeholder involvement</p>	<p>Yes. Included semistructured interviews with 26 AI researchers, geopolitical experts, and former policymakers. Stakeholders informed scenario testing and refinement.</p>															

Report 10: Quantifying AI's Economic Potential: Growth Differentials Between Assistive and Autonomous Development Scenarios

Author: Sytsma, T.

Date: 2025

Institution: RAND Corporation

The study focuses on comparing the economic growth of a future where AI remains an assistant to the economic growth in a future where AI becomes an independent agent. To achieve this, the author uses an extensive methodology, comparing and contrasting the two futures with each other. The main method is a modified endogenous growth model, enhanced by Monte Carlo simulation to predict the years 2025-2045. It rather models two extremes of the two scenarios than realistic ones to offer an overview of economic benefits that can be held against risks for policymakers. Following the models, Sytsma finds that there is faster economic growth in the agent scenario, however the tool scenario performs better in a small number of simulations where AI agents stay inefficient. In this report, Sytsma did not aim to predict which scenario would happen but quantified the economic stakes of AGI development to inform debates about balancing economic gains with risks.

Focal issue	Economic growth implications of advanced AI systems; comparing futures in which AI remains an assistant tool vs. futures where AGI agents can independently perform labour.
Goal of exercise	To estimate and compare the long-term economic growth effects of AI as Tool vs. AGI and to use that to inform policy debates
Methodology	Quantitative scenario modelling using a two-sector endogenous growth model inspired by Romer (1990), Jones (1995), and Bloom et al (2020). It uses economic growth theory, Monte Carlo simulation (1,000 simulations), Latin hypercube sampling, sensitivity analysis, regression/random forest analysis, and scenario comparison. The scenarios are two scenarios called "Tool World" and "Agent World", AI is used as an assistive tool in the first and is an autonomous agent in the latter.
Time-horizon	2045 (20 years from 2025)
Geographical scope	Primarily used US demographic and economic data, but it is intended to represent advanced economies more generally
Drivers of change/critical uncertainties	AI autonomy vs. AI used as a tool
Number of scenarios	2 scenarios
Stakeholder involvement	Only the researcher

Report 11: Reference Foresight Scenarios: Scenarios on the Global Standing of the EU in 2040.

Authors: Vesnic-Alujevic, L., Muench, S., & Stoermer, E.

Date: 2023

Institution: Publications Office of the European Union, Joint Research Centre, European Commission.

This JRC report develops reference foresight scenarios for the global standing of the European Union in 2040. The authors explicitly use an inductive scenario-building approach: instead of starting from two preselected drivers in a 2x2 matrix, they combine multiple factors, assumptions, and issue areas into broad scenario storylines. The process was participatory and iterative, using the Oxford Scenario Planning Approach with more than 100 experts across European Commission services, academia, industry, think tanks, civil society, and EU institutions. The Oxford Scenario Planning Approach is a learner-centered, iterative method that creates a small set of plausible (not probable) future scenarios to help individuals and organizations reframe their understanding of present contexts and develop strategies for navigating turbulent, uncertain, novel, and ambiguous (TUNA) situations.

The team first identified 49 assumptions, then researched seven issue areas (geopolitics, technology, environmental sustainability, economy, global social values, regulatory environment, and demographics) and translated these into factor cards. In several workshops, participants selected and linked factor cards into 22 micro-narratives, which were then clustered into four prototype scenarios and refined through validation workshops and interviews. The report also defines a set of contextual and transactional drivers as questions, such as which social values dominate globally, what geopolitical power looks like, how the food-water-energy-health nexus evolves, which technologies dominate, how Europe functions, and what its institutional membership looks like.

The four reference scenarios are: Storms, Endgame, Struggling Synergies, and Opposing Views.

1. Storms describes inward-looking societies, weak multilateralism, resource independence, climate adaptation without global coordination, food and water scarcity, and local technology standards; Europe is ageing, security-focused, and internally divided.
2. Endgame describes a world where wealth and competitiveness dominate, environmental collapse deepens inequality, and innovation accelerates into disruptive technologies, biomedicine, space technologies, synthetic foods, and Industry 7.0 virtualisation.
3. Struggling Synergies describes a consensus-driven climate agenda in which the world moves toward climate neutrality, but other sustainability issues are sidelined; innovation is mission-oriented, and Europe remains bureaucratic and divided by unequal social costs of transition.

Opposing Views describes a world split between a regenerative alliance and an exploitative alliance, each competing to impose its model through trade, resources, military power, and distinct technological paths, from circular economy and climate mitigation to GMOs and biomedicine. The report uses these broad scenarios to stress-test policies and widen thinking about Europe's future strategic position.

Focal issue	The global standing and geopolitical role of the European Union in 2040, including how megatrends in geopolitics, technology, sustainability, economy, social values, regulation, and demography might shape the EU's position, security, and soft power in an uncertain world.
Goal of exercise	To develop reference foresight scenarios that help EU-level decision-makers test policies, rethink assumptions, and build resilience under conditions of turbulence, uncertainty, novelty, and ambiguity (TUNA), especially in the context of open strategic autonomy and the global-standing debate.
Methodology	A participatory scenario-building process using the Oxford Scenario Planning Approach: identifying assumptions, researching key trends, clustering "factor cards" into micro-narratives, and consolidating them into four broad reference scenarios; validated through workshops and expert interviews.
Time-horizon	2040; the scenarios project the EU's global standing over roughly the next 15–20 years from the publication date.
Geographical scope	Global, with a focus on the European Union and its relations with major powers, regions, and multilateral institutions (e.g., Asia, the Global South, NATO-type alliances, and EU-centric regulatory regimes).
Drivers of change/critical uncertainties	Key drivers and uncertainties cluster around: geopolitics (alliances, military spending, hybrid threats), technology (AI, automation, space, cyber), environmental sustainability (climate change, resource scarcity, energy transition), economy (trade, debt, green-vs fossil-intensive sectors, de-growth debates), social values (trust, populism, multilateralism vs bloc-thinking), regulatory environment (global vs fragmented standards), and demography (ageing, migration, labour market shifts)
Number of scenarios	Four reference scenarios are developed and named: Storms, Endgame, Struggling synergies, and Opposing views. Each scenario is internally coherent, covers distinct combinations of drivers, and is meant to be used as a set, not a single "best" future.
Stakeholders involvement	The scenario-building process engaged more than 100 internal and external experts across EU-level institutions (Commission, Parliament, Council, EIB, EEAS, etc.), academia, industry, think tanks, and civil society; the core work was carried out by a 20-service informal working group of the European Commission and the JRC EU Policy Lab, using online workshops and interviews for validation and refinement.

2.3 Peer-reviewed Exploratory Scenario Studies

This section concentrates exploratory scenario studies in the peer-reviewed literature from which a standardised set of information was extracted for each study to facilitate comparison. It is the same table as in the previous section 2.2.

Table 4 gives an overview of the studies in this section of peer-reviewed scenario studies. They are again ordered alphabetically.

Table 4

	Authors	Focus	Publication Date	Time horizon	No. of scenarios
12	Gerlich	The impacts of AI and geopolitical developments on global economic, societal, and security dynamics	2024	2040	2 scenarios/ impact chains
13	Sætra	The entangled futures of global governance, AI, and climate change	2026	2045	4 scenarios
14	Teigland & Wiberg	The impact of AI and digitalisation on the EU's labour market	2025	2035	4 scenarios

Report 12: Brace for Impact: Facing the AI revolution and geopolitical shifts in a future societal scenario for 2025–2040

Date: 2024

Authors: Gerlich, M.

Journal: Societies

This paper focuses on the impacts of AI and geopolitical developments on global economic, societal, and security dynamics by 2040. Gerlich uses an extensive method, by combining multiple approaches. He uses a Complex Adaptive Systems framework to investigate how AI and geopolitical developments interact and influence other factors. Moreover, he uses a 3-round Delphi survey with 30 experts, scenario matrices, and Monte Carlo simulation modelling to create numerous probabilistic futures. The Delphi study included specialists from multiple stakeholders, such as Microsoft, Google, IBM, OpenAI, the UN, World Bank, University of Cambridge.

The results are not separate scenarios, but impact chains showing how the two main factors of AI and geopolitical developments have different impacts with different probabilities that happen as a result of each other.

- Impact of AI development: The most likely negative impact is the rise of unemployment, as well as exponential speed of AI development, and increased security risks. If unemployment happens, it is also very likely that governments would not know how to handle it, which leads to internal conflicts. The exponential AI development also very likely leads to governments being overwhelmed and late to regulations. Cybercrime could lead to failing global security systems.
- Positive impacts are predicted to be improvement of sustainability research to counter climate change. Furthermore, there is a likelihood of AI aiding medical developments.
- Impact of geopolitical developments: Gerlich predicts the biggest issues to be the Russia-Ukraine war and conflicts in the Middle East. All geopolitical issues can likely lead to increased anxieties within societies.

Focal issue	The impacts of AI and geopolitical developments on global economic, societal, and security dynamics by 2040
Goal of exercise	To construct future scenarios that show the effects of AI and geopolitical shifts and to highlight the importance of forward-looking policies and international cooperation
Methodology	Complex Adaptive Systems (CAS) framework to investigate how the two main factors in this study (AI and geopolitical shifts) can influence other things.

	<p>Figure 1. CAS framework [21].</p> <p>Mixed methods approach combining:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Delphi method (3 rounds, 30 expert panel); 2. Multiple scenario analysis with a scenario matrix; 3. Probabilistic modelling via Monte Carlo simulation <p>The author presents impact chains with assigned probabilities</p>
Time-horizon	2040 (from 2025)
Geographical scope	Global
Drivers of change/critical uncertainties	<p>Two domains of AI and geopolitical AI: rate of adoption, exponential speed of technological change, AI-driven unemployment, cybersecurity risks, AI in medical/technical fields; AI sustainability solutions; loss of trust in humans</p> <p>Figure 3. Simplified graphic display of the impact chain for geo-political developments.</p>
Number of scenarios	2 impact chains
Stakeholder involvement	In the Delphi study there were 30 senior specialists from organisations including Microsoft, Google, IBM, OpenAI, Amazon, the UN, World Bank, WEF, LSE, University of Cambridge, and the Centre for Strategic and International Studies

Report 13: Four Visions On The Future Of Global Governance, AI, And Climate Change. AI & Society

Authors: Saeltra, H. S. & Rogerson, E

Date: 2026

Journal: AI and Society

This paper by Saeltra and Rogerson (2026) focuses on the entangled futures of global governance, AI, and climate change by 2045. Their scenario development is based on Kowos and Gaßner (2008), which prioritises the holistic approach of systems thinking, understanding how multiple different factors interact to cause a whole. They illustrated this approach in a combination table of the three factors of global governance, AI, and climate change. The scenarios are presented as speculative sci-fi narratives.

1. **Under a Texan Sun:** about CEO Charlie of the US company Neos, that originally built military AI, now owns armed forces and builds domes with genetically engineered life for people to live in. They compete against an Asian company that has similar products. They now present a new product of geoengineering that can alter the climate of a part of the world, but people have to pay for it, and other places' climates will get worse. (Anarcho-capitalism | High emissions | unrestricted acceleration)
2. **Strength in Unity:** about Xiu, a Chinese delegate for the UN Cosmopolitan Forum. The Forum has a lot of influence and has members from many countries, also the New United States, EU, and China. After facing horrible climate catastrophes and after an AI Cold War, China joined the Forum and together powerful nations are building towards a joint AI research centre, focused on healthcare, education, sciences, and joint goals. (Decentralised and norms-based organisation | medium emissions | AI restrain)
3. **New Venice:** about Zhiháo, A Taiwanese AI safety expert, also part of the UN, who is in New Venice. New Venice is an "ocean-bound territory" since Old Venice drowned. Taiwan and the USA have an AI rivalry. The US is more interested in generating riches with AI, while the Taiwanese delegation is very interested in climate AI to aid with climate disasters. The Taiwanese AI presentation gets the most votes, since other nations understand the importance of climate mitigation. (formalised regime-based cooperation | medium emissions | rapid acceleration)
4. **The Planetary Intelligence Division:** about Ndei, who was just voted head of the Planetary Intelligence Division, to lead AI away from autonomous warfare, which was banned years before after devastating the planet, and towards helping Climate. (World state | low emissions | controlled, intensive use)

Focal issue	The entangled futures of global governance, AI, climate change, and their relations																				
Goal of exercise	To expand collective imagination of plausible futures, spark debate about fostering sustainability and justice, demonstrate a method for mapping potential future worlds																				
Methodology	<p>scenario development and analysis (Kowos and Gaßner, 2008). Vital to that is a holistic approach, namely systems thinking, to understand how all factors interact.</p> <p>3-factor combination table</p> <div style="text-align: right; font-size: small;">AI & SOCIETY</div> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <caption>Table 1 Four scenarios and combinations of key factors</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Scenario</th> <th>Global governance</th> <th>Climate change</th> <th>Artificial intelligence</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Anarchical society (anarcho-capitalism)</td> <td>High emissions (RCP 8.5)</td> <td>Unrestricted acceleration</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Decentralized, norms-based cooperation (English school)</td> <td>Medium emissions (≈RCP 4.5-6.0)</td> <td>Restraint</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Formalized regime-based cooperation (neoliberal Institutionalism)</td> <td>Medium emissions (≈RCP 4.5-6.0)</td> <td>Rapid acceleration</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>World state (cosmopolitan governance)</td> <td>Low emissions (RCP 2.6)</td> <td>Controlled, intensive use</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Scenarios presented as speculative/scifi narratives.</p>	Scenario	Global governance	Climate change	Artificial intelligence	1	Anarchical society (anarcho-capitalism)	High emissions (RCP 8.5)	Unrestricted acceleration	2	Decentralized, norms-based cooperation (English school)	Medium emissions (≈RCP 4.5-6.0)	Restraint	3	Formalized regime-based cooperation (neoliberal Institutionalism)	Medium emissions (≈RCP 4.5-6.0)	Rapid acceleration	4	World state (cosmopolitan governance)	Low emissions (RCP 2.6)	Controlled, intensive use
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4	World state (cosmopolitan governance)	Low emissions (RCP 2.6)	Controlled, intensive use																		
Time-horizon	2045 (from 2025)																				
Geographical scope	Global																				
Drivers of change/critical uncertainties	<p>Three key factors, each with multiple trajectories</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Global governance model 2. Climate change pathway 3. AI trajectory 																				
Number of scenarios	<p>4, the scenarios are called</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Under a Texan Sun (Anarcho-capitalism High emissions unrestricted acceleration) 2. Strength in Unity (Decentralised and norms-based organisation medium emissions AI restrain) 3. New Venice (formalised regime-based cooperation medium emissions rapid acceleration) 4. The Planetary Intelligence Division (World state low emissions controlled, intensive use) 																				
Stakeholder involvement	Not mentioned. The scenarios were developed through a series of workshops between the two authors only.																				

Report 14: AI and Digitalisation's Impact on EU's Future Labour Market: Scenarios and Implications.

Authors: Teigland, R., Wiberg, M.

Date: 2025

Institution: Palgrave Macmillan

This chapter by Teigland and Wiberg (2025) discusses the impact of AI development on the EU's future labour market in 2035. It is part of a book on the depth and breadth of the EU, meaning the strength of integration between existing EU countries and the possible inclusion of more countries in the EU. The authors used a 2x2 matrix to build four scenarios. The matrix is based on the main selected drivers of change, the purpose of the technology being for exploration or efficiency and the EU's geopolitical will to integrate. The four scenarios are called "Race to the Bottom" (efficiency & integration), "The Wild West" (efficiency & no integration), "Circularity" (exploration & no integration), and "A transformed World" (exploration & integration). The scenarios range from high Chinese and US influence to a self-sufficient EU and a sustainable, cooperating world. To build these scenarios the authors did not consult experts, but simply constructed the scenarios built on future theories from research.

1. **Race to the bottom:** China in EU driver's seat (exploitation & integration)
2. The first scenario presents a world in which digital technologies and quantum computers are used for global efficiency. Chinese and American tech companies are in the driver's seat and are coordinating the EU labour market. This is due to both countries outcompeting all other countries in quantum computing. They 'divided' the rest of the world between each other to use its natural resources. The EU has a high job polarisation and significantly different work profiles across its member states: highly skilled tech/AI jobs in mining, manufacturing, and autonomous vehicles in Northern Europe and jobs in improving agriculture gain with advanced analytics in Central and Southern Europe, alongside low-skilled service jobs in local healthcare and care sectors.
3. **The Wild West:** EU in total disarray (exploitation & no integration)
4. In this scenario digital technologies are used for security, both physical and online, due to deep global disorder. The EU is held together by national security concerns against organised crime and widespread global unrest, leading to higher militarisation. Fake news using deepfake-technologies are widespread and undermine democracy by influencing elections. The labour market lies in total chaos due to severe economic decline. High-tech jobs remain within national defence and security, while most people work in low-skill and low-tech jobs such as food-production, repair or waste management.
5. **Circularity:** EU as sustainable and resilient island (exploration & no integration)
6. In the third scenario digital technologies are used for fostering a self-sufficient EU. A significantly strengthened EU prioritises industrial policies, creating high-tech jobs across all sectors, especially in renewable technologies and sustainability. The EU built a quantum computer and increased innovation by a change of funding scheme for tech startups.

Innovation is driven by AI and the EU builds a labour market where individuals continuously reskill with help of generative AI.

7. **A transformed world:** the sky is the limit (exploration & integration)
8. Digital technologies and quantumization have brought about an entirely new world. Knowledge of ideas and innovation are shared freely among countries, leading to peaceful innovation in sustainability and AI. Healthcare increases worldwide, as countries pool resources and knowledge. People have a three-day workweek and enjoy an extensive leisure industry.

Focal issue	Impact of AI and digitalisation on the EU's labour market, which also has an impact on the main book's theme "the depth and breadth of the EU" (breadth refers to the widening of the EU, such as including new member states. The depth refers to strengthening the integration between existing members).
Goal of exercise	Explore alternative futures for the EU labour market in 2035 and derive policy recommendations to achieve a desirable future.
Methodology	2x2 matrix: They specify the use of "disciplined imagination" (Weick, 1989), where they simply construct future theories and then present future scenarios.
Time-horizon	2035, 10 years in the future
Geographical scope	EU, but scenarios mention many other countries and continents
Drivers of change/critical uncertainties	1. Purpose of technology (exploration vs. efficiency). Based on the idea of exploration vs. exploitation; embracing uncertainty and discovering innovative solutions vs. maximising efficiency by optimising processes. It's a paradox that highlights the challenge of being both innovative and optimising known processes. 2. Geopolitical will to integrate (no will vs. full will)
Number of scenarios	The four the scenarios are called 1. Race to the bottom: China in EU driver's seat (exploitation & integration) 2. The Wild West: EU in total disarray (exploitation & no integration) 3. Circularity: EU as sustainable and resilient island (exploration & no integration) 4. A transformed world: the sky is the limit (exploration & integration)
Stakeholder involvement	Not mentioned, only academic exercise

2.4 Other studies

The below section presents a study that is treated separately because it is a foresight study using the Delphi method instead of scenario building:

	Authors	Focus	Publication Date	Time horizon	No. of scenarios
15	Favino et al.	Security challenges and opportunities arising from Key Enabling Technologies, such as AI	2025	2030	No scenarios, but general future directions

Report 15: Emerging risks and opportunities for EU internal security stemming from new technologies

Authors: Favino, R., Conte, N., De Maleville, A., Garcia Monreal, E., Montanari, E., Paganini, A., Sangiorgi, M., & Sfalagkiaris, C.

Date: 2025

Institution: Publications Office of the European Union, Joint Research Centre, European Commission

This foresight study examines how new technologies may reshape EU internal security by 2030, with a focus on resilience of critical infrastructures and fighting crime and terrorism. It is based on horizon scanning, literature analysis, signal collection, and a Delphi survey with 63 experts, and it aims to help policymakers and law enforcement agencies anticipate both opportunities and risks. The report clearly distinguishes between contextual factors and the technology signals themselves. It identifies 107 contextual factors and groups them into 31 drivers, 12 enablers, and 10 barriers, using STEEPL as an organising framework for social, technological, economic, environmental, political, legal, and informational influences. The main known trends include the need for a skilled workforce, ageing populations, inequality, polarisation, market demand, funding and R&D investment, energy prices, dependence on global supply chains, and the concentration of technological assets in the hands of a few private actors.

The report also identifies major sources of uncertainty in the form of interlinked technological and governance dynamics. These include the rise of cybersecurity monopolies, the increasing intelligence, decentralisation and connectivity of technologies, hybrid threats, the balance between innovation and regulation, and the extent to which international cooperation on cybersecurity and data governance can be achieved. It further notes uncertainty around ethics, trust, privacy, court decisions, and the practical ability of law enforcement agencies to use new tools under future legal constraints. The report discusses weak signals, and it treats them as early indicators detected through text mining and scientometrics rather than as a separate scenario layer. It explains that weak signals were drawn from Scopus, PATSTAT, CORDIS, EMM, and other sources, and it gives examples such as smuggling with drones, biometric identification and data protection, social media radicalisation, new and more potent drugs, nanotechnology, blockchain technology, digital twin for security, advanced sensing technologies, phishing detection using machine learning, vertical take-off and landing remotely piloted systems, proxy ware misuse, edge AI, 6G networks, AI-powered security, and raw material tracking.

Overall, the study is not a scenario report in the strict sense. Rather, it maps what the authors see as stable trends, contested uncertainties, and early weak signals in order to inform EU security policy and technology preparedness.

Focal issue	Emerging security challenges and opportunities for EU internal security stemming from Key Enabling Technologies (KETs) such as AI, advanced sensing, blockchain, drones, and related technologies, in the domains of Resilience of Critical Entities and Fighting Crime and Terrorism
Goal of exercise	To support EU policy development and Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs) by identifying how KETs may transform internal-security dynamics by 2030, and to provide evidence-based recommendations on risk mitigation and capability building
Methodology	A foresight exercise combining horizon scanning (455 raw signals → 110 selected signals), a Delphi survey with 63 experts, and network analysis (interlinkages between KETs and signals); contextual-factors assessment via adapted STEEPL-I and “Futures Triangle” framing.
Time-horizon	Forward-looking with an explicit 2030 time-horizon for assessing how KETs may shape internal-security risks and opportunities
Geographical scope	European Union-wide, with reference to EU-level policies, Horizon Europe, and transnational internal-security functions (e.g. protecting critical entities and combating crime and terrorism across Member States).
Drivers of change/critical uncertainties	Key drivers and contextual factors grouped by STEEPL-I: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social: ageing population, polarisation, ethical values, data-driven behaviour, workforce skills gaps • Technological: AI-driven automation, decentralised and digital infrastructure, faster-evolving cyber-threats and deepfakes. • Economic: R&D investment, market demand, supply-chain dependence, energy prices, technological monopolies. • Environmental: Climate-change-driven innovation and green-tech adoption • Political & Legal: Concentration of tech assets in few private actors, regulatory gaps, hybrid-threats, Court-driven limits on LEA technologies, and need for international cooperation
Number of scenarios	The report does not propose a fixed set of labelled scenarios (e.g., “4 scenarios”); instead, it identifies trends, risks, and opportunities across KETs and contextual factors, and then formulates general future-oriented directions (e.g., more AI-centric, more decentralised, more contested data-governance) rather than a discrete scenario-set.
Stakeholder involvement	Core stakeholder groups involved: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal-security and law-enforcement professionals (e.g., EU-level and Member-State LEAs). • Technology and policy experts on Key Enabling Technologies (KETs such as AI, blockchain, drones, advanced sensing)

2.5 Synthesis and Discussion

After presenting the extensive information of all collected studies, we use the findings to inform our own exploratory scenario-building exercise. We take inspiration from the parameters of scenarios presented in the studies and aim to fill in the gaps we discovered. We focus on the selected parameters

Time horizon

Firstly, deciding the time horizon for the scenarios is important. Our findings converge at 2030-32, where seven out of the fifteen studies set their scenarios. 2030 as the de facto time horizon is likely due to it being close enough to be relevant for policy, but also far enough away to allow multiple diverging futures. The other studies are set unevenly, in 2040 (Vesnic-Alujevic et al., 2023) and 2050 (Pasimeni & Dotti, 2025), while all academic studies are set further in the future as well at 2035 (Teigland & Wiberg, 2025), 2040 (Gerlich, 2024), and 2045 (Saetra & Rogerson, 2025). Sytsma (2025) also projects possible futures as far as 2045. Two RAND studies on AGI futures (Chessen & Chowdhury, 2025; Pavel et al., 2025) deliberately avoid setting a year at all. Yet, completing this approach in detail is time-intensive, therefore needing to be considered carefully. For our HARNCESS scenario-building, these findings recommend 2030 as a fitting time-horizon. If we decide to choose a different one, we need to be explicit about why we do so.

Focal issue

The studies have different common topical foci. Here, the biggest divergences between studies lies in the placement of AI-development and AI capabilities. Some studies take the trajectories of AI capabilities as a central axis, while others place them as one input amongst others into broader societal, economic, or security developments. For our own scenario study we need to decide deliberately where AI sits in this respect, since there is no strong consensus in the literature. The most common shared topic of the studies is the capability of AI or AGI. The trajectories of AI capabilities are scenario-axis in seven studies (Chessen & Chowdhury, 2025; GovUK, 2024; Hobbs et al. 2026; Özcan et al. 2025; Pavel et al., 2025; Sytsma, 2025; Gerlich, 2024). This reflects how dominant the question of how fast and capable AI will become is in current foresight work. Cybersecurity is also a recurrent theme in the literature, mainly in three studies (Cleaveland et al., 2023; Favino et al., 2025; Mattioli & Malatras, 2024). In these, AI is often one main driver that impacts cybersecurity instead of being the central focus. Increased cybersecurity risks are linked to the variable of AI capabilities as well, indicating the importance of this factor. Another common topic is the economic aspect of AI futures. Three studies (Crotta et al., 2025; Sytsma, 2025; Teigland & Wiberg, 2025) primarily discuss AI-development through the lens of economic growth, competitiveness, and work. However, all other studies also mention economic impacts of AI, as it is a future change that nearly everyone will be impacted by and a logical extrapolation of the economic influence AI already has.

Geographical scope of the study

Multiple studies heavily focus on the geopolitical standing of certain countries in an AI-shaped future, may it be the EU, US, or UK (GovUK, 2024; Pasimeni & Dotti, 2025; Pavel et al., 2025; Teigland & Wiberg, 2025; Vesnic-Alujević et al., 2023). Such focus is common in studies funded by related organisations, such as the EU Joint Research Centre. A clear geographic anchor also helps centre the scenario creation. Yet, AI development and governance is globalised, so too narrow focus risks creating scenarios that treat the main region in a vacuum, disconnected from the rest of the world. Scenarios should stay geographically focused, while still accounting for external dependencies and influence from other places. Lastly, the connection between AI-development and climate change is also prevalent in the literature. While only one study treats it as a main focus (Sætra, 2025), nearly every study mentions the positive and negative environmental impact AI can have. As environmental crises are another vital topic of futures studies, including it in future scenarios makes sense, yet adds a layer of uncertainty.

Drivers of change

Drawing on all 15 studies, the drivers of change can be organised into three tiers: (1) predetermined elements treated as constants, as well as strong trends; (2) critical uncertainties that are used to branch into different futures; (3) weak signals that are less-established and rarely mentioned.

Predetermined Elements and Strong Trends

These are patterns the literature treats as near-certain and they appear consistently across studies that our own scenario should likely treat them as shared constants.

- Continued increase in AI investment, even if the pace is contested
- Increasing digitalisation and automation pressure on labour markets
- Rising dependence on technology infrastructures and a small number of dominant providers
- US-China strategic rivalry ongoing in relation to AI and technology governance
- Climate change as an active pressure on infrastructure, resources, policy

Critical Uncertainties

These are the variables used to construct diverging futures. They are also the axes of scenario matrices.

- AI capability progress: gradual, exponential, stalling
- Centralisation vs. decentralisation of AI/AGI
- Public vs. private control of AI/AGI
- Geopolitical stability vs. volatility, including degree of international cooperation vs. fragmentation
- Speed and depth of regulatory response to technological change
- Degree of societal trust in AI and related institutions
- Alignment between AI systems and human values and the degree of human oversight retained

Weak Signals

These signals are mentioned only sparsely in a few studies. They are worth monitoring, but not central in scenario construction.

- Digital fatigue among older generations as a brake on technology adoption
- Geoengineering as commercial climate intervention
- Space-based infrastructure dependence
- AI-powered biometric identification and new synthetic drugs

Literature Gaps

There are several gaps in the literature for an EU-focused exercise on AI futures such as we want to create. We aim to fill them in our own exploratory scenario workshops.

First, the agency of citizens and social movements is almost entirely missing. Across all 15 studies, the actors who shaped AI futures are overwhelmingly governments, corporations, and international bodies. Civil society appears mainly as a stakeholder, sometimes consulted in workshops (GovUK, 2024; Vesnic-Alujević et al., 2023), but is rarely treated as an active driver of change capable of shaping outcomes through resistance. Moreover, non-Western countries and the Global South are largely absent as protagonists. The geographic scope of studies is mainly EU-, US-, or UK-centred. Where the Global South is mentioned, it tends to be as a passive recipient of technology diffusion or exclusion rather than a source of distinct trajectories or demands. Despite the EU being mentioned as an actor in AI's future, many the scenarios do not deeply dive into EU digital sovereignty as a driver; only reports funded by the EU dive into the topic. Few studies engage directly with the EU's capacity (or incapacity) to control its own digital infrastructure and data flows independent of the US or China. Given that our scenario study is part of an EU-focused project, it is a significant blind-spot to account for. Also absent from scenarios are within-society distributional effects, meaning who specifically benefits or loses beyond broader framings such as 'labour market polarisation.' A few studies engage with this, such as Teigland & Wiberg (2025) presenting regional labour markets split in Europe between north and south. Yet, most treat societal impact at a higher level of abstraction without clearly examining which groups bear the costs or capture the gains. Lastly, although climate change and environmental impacts of AI are mentioned in most studies, the analyses stay shallow. AI is mentioned to impact the environment, but specific chain-reactions and concrete interaction with electronic waste, data centres, water and energy consumption, or pollution, is lacking. Notably, Sytsma (2025) and Hobbs et al (2026) do not mention environmental impacts despite focusing on AI scaling, where both factors go hand in hand. Given how central AI scaling and growing AI capabilities are to most scenario studies, it is vital to include environmental impacts as well.) Vesnic-Alujević et al., (2023) and Hobbs et al (2026) do not mention environmental impacts despite focusing on AI scaling, where both factors go hand in hand. Given how AI scaling and growing AI capabilities are to most scenario studies, it is vital to include environmental impacts as well.

3 SCENARIO WORKSHOP PLAN, FALL 2026

The HARNESSE scenario-building exercise consists of two stages. The first stage produces a set of domain-general scenarios depicting plausible futures of AI and data flows within the EU governance context, developed collectively by HARNESSE DCs for the project through three structured workshops running from September to November 2026. The second stage, running roughly from December 2026 to February 2027, will build on this domain-general set, but the focus is on three specific dissertation topics, namely, The Ethics of Foundational AI Models (D6), Multi-Level Governance of AI in Decentralised Energy Systems (DC7), and Anticipatory Ethics of Self-Sovereign Identity (DC8). In that second stage, there are two options to choose from left at the discretion of each DC to best fit their dissertation work. The first option is to use domain-general scenarios to stress-test EU or government policies, citizens' actions, and collective strategies related to their topic. The second option is to elaborate on domain-specific scenarios to create more detailed domain-specific scenarios in their domain of interest. The second stage of HARNESSE scenarios will be essentially written by each DC, but may draw on additional input from domain experts or stakeholders interviewed individually and collectively, as means to ensure that, although HARNESSE scenarios are expert-based rather than participatory due to resource constraints, the resulting scenarios will be informed by actors involved not only in academia, but also public policy and/or civil society and/or industry.

As part of the training offered to DCs by the HARNESSE project, Dr Yashar Saghai, an expert in technology ethics and futures studies with experience as a futures practitioner, delivered a presentation in the second HARNESSE week-long Workshop (June 2026) introducing anticipatory practices and methods for enhancing the ethical and social evaluation of uncertain AI futures. The presentation focused on two methods used when facing deep uncertainty that precludes prediction: exploratory scenario-building and normative visioning exercises. This training has both helped us understand our workshop design options and provided much of the source material drawn on in the discussion below. Dr Saghai will also facilitate and guide the scenario workshops described in Section 3.3. The remainder of this section sets out our design choices for the domain-general exercise, the reasoning behind potential parameters chosen, and the workshop schedule through which it will be delivered.

3.1 Focal Issue and time-horizon

The focal issue of the workshops will be specified during the September 2026 workshop. However, our initial idea (to be critically discussed with scenario building team members) is the future of AI sovereignty in the EU, which may also serve as the basis for stress-testing EU policies and actions across the three domains on which the DCs are working. The choice of sovereignty as the organising problem is deliberate. Digital and technological sovereignty has become a clear strategic priority for the EU, especially evident since the introduction of the European Commission's Tech Sovereignty Package, yet our previous review of existing scenario studies (Section 2) revealed that no scenario set explicitly takes EU sovereignty as its central axis of inquiry. Specifically, we found that prominent AI-futures reports concentrate heavily on economic growth and geopolitics of countries dominating

the technology sector, while paying comparatively little attention to EU digital sovereignty, the role of civil society actors, environmental and ecological impacts, and the position of the Global South. The HARNESS scenarios will deliberately attend to some of these dimensions, both to enrich the set and to ensure relevance to the consortium's ethical, social, and economic concerns. The HARNESS workshops therefore will address an important literature gap, beyond producing outputs that may be informative for EU governance and policymaking. Additional parameters will be discussed in the workshop as well. Finally, we envision a time horizon for the exercise of five to seven years (to approximately 2032–2033). This relatively short horizon is dictated by the project timeline and by the exercise's focus on governance mechanisms and near-term policy relevance, where longer horizons would weaken the scenarios' strength for current EU instruments.

3.2 Rationale for Methodological Choices

In line with the considerations discussed in Section 1, we adopt a top-down approach to scenario construction, also known as the standard, intuitive-logics, or deductive approach, and often associated with the "2x2 matrix" method (Saghai, 2026). This approach (outlined in section 2) proceeds by first identifying axes of critical uncertainty, then deriving the combinatorially possible futures they generate, and finally inhabiting those futures with narrative content. We favour this approach over bottom-up methods, which build “plausible futures inductively through rich situational analysis without a predefined matrix”, and over outside-in methods, which apply a “small set of fixed archetypal future images and fill in domain-specific content within them” (Saghai 2026). As Yashar Saghai (2026) explains, “[t]he top-down approach offers a structurally clean and easily transferrable process, is transparent and therefore defensible to the audiences for whom the scenarios are intended, while being time-efficient comparatively to alternatives...it is also flexible in terms of budget and output length, making it well suited to systematic comparison across the three domains and accommodative of different narrative styles”.

To structure the scenario space, we would ideally converge on two drivers of uncertainty (to make the scenario exercise manageable), each with three possible states, which will be further discussed and refined with members of the scenario building team at the outset. The selection of these drivers of uncertainty will be informed by the gaps in the existing literature. Two drivers with three states each yield a scenario space of $3^2 = 9$ combinations. However, this space should be reduced to a more manageable set of four scenarios by eliminating internally inconsistent combinations and by setting aside those that are less challenging or analytically productive. Given the modest size of the scenario space, this reduction will be made during our workshops, and morphological analysis will be used only if the scenario space is much larger.

3.3 Scenario Building Team and Expert-Based Approach

The scenario building team for the domain-general stage will be the HARNESS DCs. The exercise is therefore expert-based within the consortium, justified by the relevant expertise we hold across computer science, law, and ethics, which the structure of the MSCA scheme invites to bring together to cover technical, regulatory, and normative dimensions of the uncertainties of the futures of AI

sovereignty in the EU. After the third workshop, the resulting draft will be shared with HARNESSES supervisors and, where appropriate, with other relevant experts for additional feedback before finalisation.

We have chosen not to conduct a participatory scenario-building exercise at this stage for two reasons related to the project resource availability: first, our project does not have the budget or the staffing required to design and facilitate participatory scenarios involving citizens and/or external experts. Second, and more substantively, broader stakeholder engagement is already planned for the second stage of the project (approximately December 2026 to February 2027) to ensure the results will be informed by various perspectives, not limited to academia. At that stage, engagement will be directed either toward stress-testing policies, actions, and strategies against the domain-general scenarios and/or toward developing the domain-specific scenarios based on that set.

3.4 Workshop Schedule

The domain-general exercise will be delivered through three online workshops, interspersed with drafting and revision phases:

- **Workshop 1** (early September 2026) will establish the collective decision on scenario focal issue, scope, parameters, and drivers of change, and will construct the scenario space. A first draft will follow in subsequent weeks, in which the team will produce initial scenario narratives based on the space agreed in Workshop 1.
- **Workshop 2** (early October 2026) will gather feedback on these drafts and will open discussion of the pathways leading to each future. A second draft will follow in subsequent weeks, in which the team will revise the initial scenarios and will add draft pathways to each future end-state.
- **Workshop 3** (early November 2026) will be dedicated to revision and validation of the scenarios, as final internal consistency and plausibility check before the set is considered complete.
- Following Workshop 3, the WP3 will undertake revisions in subsequent November weeks, producing a complete draft. At the end of November, this draft will be shared with supervisors and potentially other experts for feedback, with final revisions carried out in weeks 2–3 of December 2026.

This three-workshop structure will complete the domain-general stage of the exercise. As mentioned above, the domain-general scenario set, i.e., the output, will serve as shared input for the project's second stage (December 2026 to February 2027).

CONCLUSION

This report has set out the anticipatory methods for exploring the joint ethical, social, and economic implications of AI and data flows, alongside the evolving regulatory frameworks and compliance mechanisms shaping these technologies in the EU. As Section 1 established, scenario building is particularly well-suited to this purpose because it holds open a plurality of plausible futures rather than converging on a single predicted outcome, a capacity demanded by the deep uncertainty and complexity characterising both the technologies under analysis and the regulatory landscape governing them. The rapid literature review in Section 2 informed the design of the HARNESS workshops while also revealing that prominent AI-futures reports concentrate heavily on economic growth and geopolitics, paying comparatively little attention to EU digital sovereignty, civil society actors, environmental and ecological impacts, and the position of the Global South. By taking the future of AI sovereignty in the EU as its focal issue, the HARNESS scenario set is positioned to address this gap. Section 3 translated these findings into our chosen workshop design: a top-down approach to be delivered through three structured workshops running from September to November 2026. The resulting domain-general scenarios will be used both to stress-test EU policies, actions, and strategies or as the foundation for the three domain-specific scenarios on the topics of The Ethics of Foundational AI Models (D6), Multi-Level Governance of AI in Decentralised Energy Systems (DC7), and Anticipatory Ethics of Self-Sovereign Identity (DC8). The anticipatory methods established here will therefore underpin the remainder of WP3's work.

DECLARATION OF USE OF AI-ASSISTED TECHNOLOGIES

In section 2, information of the studies was extracted using Claude Sonnet 4.5 (Anthropic, 2025) by providing the full PDF text as input and prompting the model to populate the used extraction table. Extracted fields were subsequently verified manually against the original source document by DCs to ensure accuracy. Where discrepancies were identified, the source document took precedence. Claude was moreover used to check spelling and grammar, as well as syntax clarity. All content and claims were verified by the authors and are their responsibilities.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Armanto, A. R. A. (2024). Futures Participation as Anticipatory Practice — What do Futures Workshops do? *European Journal of Futures Research*, 12(3), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40309-024-00226-4>
- Barnett, J., Kieslich, K., Sinchai, J., & Diakopoulos, N. (2025). Scenarios in Computing Research: A Systematic Review of the Use of Scenario Methods for Exploring the Future of Computing Technologies in Society. *ArXiv*. <https://doi.org/doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2506.05605>
- Börjeson, L., Höjer, M., Dreborg, K. H., Ekvall, T., & Finnveden, G. (2006). Scenario Types and Techniques: Towards a User's Guide. *Futures*, 38(7), 723–739. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2005.12.002>
- Bourgeois, R., Karuri-Sebina, G., & Feukeu, K. E. (2024). The future as a public good: decolonising the future through anticipatory participatory action research. *Foresight*, 26(4), 533–549. <https://doi.org/10.1108/FS-11-2021-0225>
- Brey, P. A. E. (2012). Anticipatory Ethics for Emerging Technologies. *Nanoethics*, 6(1), 1–13.
- Chessen, M., & Chowdhury, S. (2025). *Pivots and pathways on the road to artificial general intelligence futures*. RAND Corporation. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.7249/PEA4178-1>
- Cleaveland, A., Cohn, A., Nagamine, M., Thomas, D., Rimsky Vernon, A., Bouckaert, J., & Joshi, A. (2023). *Report Cybersecurity Futures 2030: New Foundations*. CNA Institute for Public Research. https://cltc.berkeley.edu/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/WEF_Cybersecurity_Futures_2030_New_Foundations_2023.pdf
- Crotta, F., Betti, F., Di Battista, A., Elsner, M., Karunska, K., & Zahidi, S. (2025). *Four Futures for the New Economy: Geoeconomics and Technology in 2030*. World Economic Forum. https://reports.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Four_Futures_for_the_New_Economy_Geoeconomics_and_Technology_in_2030_2025.pdf
- Favino, R., Conte, N., De Maleville, A., Monreal, G., Sangiorgi, A., & Sfalagkiaris, M. (2025). *Emerging Risks and Opportunities for EU Internal Security stemming from New Technologies*. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2760/7979295>
- Gerlich, M. (2024). Brace for Impact: Facing the AI Revolution and Geopolitical Shifts in a Future Societal Scenario for 2025-2040. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/SSRN.4953521>
- Glenn, J. C., & The Futures Group International. (2009). Scenarios. *Futures Research Methodology: Version 3.0*, 1–48.
- GovUK. (2024). *AI 2030 scenarios: Helping policy makers plan for the future of AI*. UK Government Office for Science, Department for Science, Innovation and Technology. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/frontier-ai-capabilities-and-risks-discussion-paper/ai-2030-scenarios-report-html-annex-c>
- Hiltunen, E. (2008). The Future Sign and its Three Dimensions. *Futures*, 40(3), 247–260. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2007.08.021>
- Hobbs, H., Docherty, D., Aranda, L., Sugimoto, K., Perset, K., & Kierzenkowski, R. (2026). *Exploring Possible AI Trajectories through 2030*.

- Mattioli, R., & Malatras, A. (2024). *Foresight Cybersecurity Threats for 2030*. <https://doi.org/10.2824/349493>
- Özcan, B., Juijn, D., Graabak, J., & Bogerd, S. (2025). *Advanced AI: Possible Futures*. Centre for Future Generations. <https://cfg.eu/advanced-ai-possible-futures/>
- Pasimeni, P., & Dotti, N. F. (2025). *The Demographic Turn Actions Needed for Research, Innovation and Policy in Europe*. <https://doi.org/10.2777/8349625>
- Pavel, B., Ke, I., Smith, G., Brown-Heidenreich, S., Sabbag, L., Acharya, A., & Mahmood, Y. (2025). *How Artificial General Intelligence Could Affect The Rise and Fall Of Nations: Visions for Potential AGI Futures*. RAND Corporation. https://www.rand.org/pubs/research_reports/RRA3034-2.html
- Poli, R. (2022). Foresight. In V. P. Glăveanu (Ed.), *The Palgrave Encyclopedia of the Possible* (1st ed., pp. 577–583). Springer International Publishing.
- Popper, R. (2008). How are Foresight Methods Selected? *Foresight*, 10(6), 62–89. <https://doi.org/10.1108/14636680810918586>
- Sabol, T., & Delina, R. (2004). *Scenario Planning*. 8, 942–956. www.prisma-eu.org
- Sætra, H. S. (2025). The Rise of the Research Automaton: Science as Process or Product in the Era of Generative AI? *AI and Society*, 41(3), 1865–1879. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S00146-025-02557-7/TABLES/2>
- Saghai, Y. (2026). Technology Ethics and Futures Studies. *Presentation for the 2nd MSCA HARNESS Training Workshop: Building Interdisciplinary Excellence in AI, Law and Ethics (Avignon)*.
- Sytsma, T. (2025). *Quantifying AI's Economic Potential Growth Differentials Between Assistive and Autonomous Development Scenarios Research Report*. www.rand.org/about/research-integrity.
- Teigland, R., & Wiberg, M. (2025). AI and Digitalisation's Impact on EU's Future Labour Market: Scenarios and Implications. *The Depth and Size of the European Union in a Time of War: Interdisciplinary European Studies*, 223–249. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-83441-7_10/TABLES/1
- van Asselt, M., van 't Klooster, van Notten, P. W. F., & Smits, L. (2010). *Foresight in Action: Developing Policy-Oriented Scenarios* (M. van Asselt, Ed.). Earthscan.
- Varum, C. A., & Melo, C. (2010). Directions in Scenario Planning Literature - A Review of the Past Decades. *Futures*, 42(4), 355–369. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2009.11.021>
- Vesnic-Alujević, L., Muench, S., & Stoermer, E. (2023). *Reference Foresight Scenarios: Scenarios on the Global Standing of the EU in 2040*. <https://doi.org/doi:10.2760/490501>